

D1.3

Report on impact and contribution of existing SCS and B2B Labels

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Report on impact and contribution of existing SCS and B2B Labels

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Partners short names

TUB	Technische Universitat Berlin
UNITELMA	Università degli studi Unitelma di Roma
UNI	Ente Italiano di Normazione
AUA	Geoniko Panepistimion Athinon
USC	Universidad de Santiago de Compostela
APRE	Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea
NOVA	Institut for politische und Okologische Innovation GMBH
BB	Better Biomass
BAM	Bundesanstalt fuer Materialforschung und Pruefung
RSB	Roundtable on Sustainable Biomaterials Association
ISEAL	Iseal Alliance

Abbreviations

ASC	Aquaculture Stewardship Council
CAB Abstracts	Centre for Agriculture and Bioscience Abstracts
EU	European Union
FSC	Forest Stewardship Council
GFC	Green Food Certified
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
IFOAM	International Federation of Organic Agriculture Movements
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
MSPO	Malaysia Sustainable Palm Oil Standard
RSPO	Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil
SAN	Sustainable Agriculture Network
SCS	Sustainability Certification Schemes
USDA	United States Department of Agriculture

About STAR4BBS

The overall aim of STAR4BBS is to maximize the potential of Sustainability Certification Schemes (SCS) and labels to support a successful transition to a sustainable bio-based economy. STAR4BBS is developing a new monitoring system for assessing the effectiveness and robustness of existing international and EU SCS, B2B labels, and related traceability systems applicable to biological feedstocks and bio-based materials and products, thus creating the foundations to support achieving the harmonization between schemes and transparency in global and EU trade flows. Learn more at www.STAR4BBS.eu

About ISEAL

ISEAL is the global membership organisation for ambitious, collaborative, and transparent sustainability systems. We support and challenge our members to continually improve their impact for the benefit of people and planet. ISEAL also works to understand the impacts of sustainability standards and other market-based tools on key sustainability issues and manages Evidensia (www.evidensia.eco) – an open access platform that helps stakeholders access credible impacts research. Learn more at www.ISEALAlliance.org

About Oxford Systematic Reviews (OXSREV)

Oxford Systematic Reviews (OXSREV®) are specialists in evidence-based solutions. They specialise in stakeholder engagement/workshops, online surveys, high impact evidence evaluation reports, systematic reviews, systematic maps, rapid reviews, peer reviewed journal articles, and interactive location-based knowledge maps. The team has successfully worked together over many years in OXSREV® to provide services to governments, NGOs, Universities, as well as to the private sector.

About Evidensia

Evidensia's mission is to put evidence at the heart of sustainability actions and decisions. With growing commitment by governments and businesses to tackle sustainability challenges, there is a need for understanding what approaches work where, why and how. Evidensia helps you access and interpret credible research on the sustainability impacts and effectiveness of supply chain initiatives and tools. It provides a portal to information and evidence and supports shared learning through its insights and analysis. Learn more at www.evidensia.eco

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Executive Summary

To help realise a transition to a sustainable circular bio-based economy, the STAR4BBS project aims to achieve increased transparency on bio-based value chains. A new fit-for-purpose monitoring system is being created to encourage harmonisation and achieve greater impact of existing Sustainability Certification Schemes (SCS) and labels. This report shares findings of one of the preliminary research tasks, the goal of which is to explore the impact and contribution of existing SCS and labels through a systematic mapping of the academic evidence base.

This research mapping focuses on Greenhouse Gas Emissions reductions enabled by SCS and labels for all bio-based value chains. Value chains outside the scope of the STAR4BBS project (i.e., food, feed, and biomass for energy) have also been included in this research mapping exercise because the same biomass and feedstock can be used in multiple value chains.

The primary question for the research mapping was:

Do sustainability certification schemes and labels, used in the bioeconomy, reduce greenhouse gas emissions?

The search conducted following the Search Protocol (Appendix 1a) returned 6,286 articles of literature from 3 bibliographic databases (Web of Science, Scopus and CAB Abstracts). After filtering, a total of 41 relevant articles were identified that form the basis of this report. Some insights from this evidence base include:

- **Impact of certifications and labels on GHG emissions**

Out of the 41 included publications, there majority of articles indicated a positive or negative impact from certification scheme to GHG emissions. The remaining articles did not present a clear conclusion about the impact of the certification. The findings reported in these studies are discussed in the main body of the report. Please also see section “2.3.10 Study Design” for more information about the robustness of the included studies.

Of the articles that showed directionality, over two thirds reported positive performance of the certified subjects when compared with non-certified or conventional systems (i.e., lower emissions), and the remaining studies demonstrated a negative performance.

For the articles that showed no directionality, there was either no non-certified comparator, or researchers were not able to demonstrate a clear difference in emissions between certified and non-certified subjects. Some studies contained too much variability across results to draw a general conclusion.

- **Studies in the evidence base**

Around three quarters of the articles (71%) were subscription-only access. This has serious implications for non-academic stakeholders who are ‘locked out’ of important sources of evidence.

Geographically, Indonesia (n=5) and Italy (n=5) were best represented in the evidence base, followed by Malaysia (n=3), Germany (n=3), the United States of America (n=3), and China (n=3).

There is an increasing trend in the numbers of publications over time, with spikes in certain years (2019).

- **Certification schemes and labels**

The research evidence base covers 16 certification schemes or labels, with the most common being the “organic” standard and label, which was used as an umbrella term in 27 studies (See the discussion section for more information). We have represented the bulk of these reports against the International Federation of Organic Agriculture Movements (IFOAM) standard that is the global agency that oversees organic certification. The other organic schemes included in the mapping were VIVA (n=2), United States Department of Agriculture (USDA) National Organic Program (n=2) and Naturland (n=2).

Other certification schemes covered by more than one piece of research are: the Forest Stewardship Council (FSC) (n=5) and the Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil (RSPO) (n=4)

- **Sectors and feedstocks/products**

The number of studies addressing GHG emissions was highest for the agriculture sector, followed by forestry and livestock. Data was reported for 32 products, of which timber products, palm oil, rice and dairy products had the highest number of studies. Most products were reported in a single study each.

- **Value chain stages**

The production phase had the largest number of studies, followed by processing, with disposal being the least represented life cycle stage. Studies in the production stage and processing stage were primarily from the agricultural sectors (n=23 and n=6 respectively).

The evidence base shows significant knowledge gaps in terms of specific certification schemes and labels, most sectors and products, and most parts of the life cycle. These evidence gaps represent a research opportunity to advance not only knowledge of impacts of certification on GHG emissions, but also to improve measuring and monitoring by certification schemes and labels themselves.

Determining whether sustainability certification schemes and labels used in the bioeconomy reduce GHG emissions is a complex and context-dependent question. There is insufficient robust evidence across the value chain, sectors, and geographic regions in the current evidence base to definitively answer this question without

further primary research. The dearth of impacts evidence on bio-based value chains is especially apparent when we consider the specific boundaries of the STAR4BBS project (i.e., excluding food, feed and bioenergy would further reduce the evidence base significantly). It is not possible to know for sure whether this will be the case for other thematic areas of interest to STAR4BBS without a similar mapping exercise. However, one could assume that such a high priority topic as GHG emissions reductions would have one of the larger evidence bases, and that mappings of other areas may find a similarly low level of evidence.

The implication for the Joint Monitoring System (JMS) under development by STAR4BBS and its sister projects is that it cannot, at this time, afford to solely rely on impacts research to benchmark the outcomes of SCS and labels. At the same time, as one of the goals of the JMS is to support improvement of SCS and labels over time, highlighting the evidence gaps could over time encourage both scheme owners and researchers to help fill these gaps.

1 Introduction

The shift toward a bio-based economy has raised concerns about the potential negative impacts associated with the rapid increase in demand for bio-based materials. Consequently, new international and national regulations, initiatives, and agreements are being implemented to manage the trade-offs along bio-based value chains. Within this context Sustainability Certification Schemes (SCS) and labels are seen as key approaches to assess the sustainability of bioproducts and neutralise these externalities. Recognizing their significance, the STAR4BBS project (www.star4bbs.eu) has been funded with the aim of guiding a successful transition to a sustainable bio-based economy by reaching greater harmonisation and effectiveness of existing SCS and labels.

1.1 Sustainability systems, certification schemes and labels

Sustainability systems are market-based initiatives that address sustainability issues by setting a standard or establishing a similar tool that defines performance levels or pathways for improvement (ISEAL, 2021). Within this ecosystem, SCS and labels are some of the earliest market-based voluntary tools used to guide action on sustainability in value chains.

SCS and labels are powerful approaches for change within the bioeconomy, and could provide a clear and standardised framework to ensure sustainable governance and management practices. These certifications incentivise producers and manufacturers to adhere to environmental and social standards and also empower consumers with the ability to make informed choices about products. By highlighting and rewarding sustainable practices, certifications can act as catalysts for systemic shifts towards environmentally and socially responsible production and consumption.

SCS and labels applicable to the value chain of bioproducts seek to effect change in several different ways. Some apply only to the production of raw materials, certifying compliance with certain production practices or attainment of set performance targets written into the standard. Some apply across the value chain, ensuring that the raw material used is produced sustainably and that certain practices are followed in the processing and manufacturing of bioproducts. Others certify end-of-life characteristics of biomaterials and bioproducts (e.g., the degree of biodegradability or recyclability).

1.2 The systematic mapping's focus and scope

The rapid proliferation of SCS and labels has led to question of their effectiveness and robustness, and the extent to which they deliver important outcomes, in line with sustainability policy priorities. This report aims to provide an overview of the available evidence of SCS and labels' impacts on GHG reductions by conducting a systematic mapping of the academic literature on this topic and supporting this with a discrete narrative review of relevant papers from the search.

To measure the multi-dimensional impact on achieving sustainability of all SCS and labels relevant to the STAR4BBS project would not be feasible given the project's timeline and budget, and so a smaller test area needed to be chosen.

After a scoping investigation and in line with D1.1's investigation into the EU's priority policy targets (STAR4BBS, 2023a), the decision was taken to focus the systematic mapping on relevant SCS and labels' contribution to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions reductions along the value chain.

Some voluntary sustainability systems and market-based approaches have been established explicitly to address and mitigate GHG emissions. These initiatives operate in diverse ways and target various stages of the supply chain. While not all SCS and labels currently have relevant requirements that expressly seek to reduce GHG emissions, they do cover many enabling practices. Given this variability, it is important to establish what evidence exists connecting certification schemes and labels that are applicable to the value chain of bio-based products to demonstrable GHG emissions reduction.

To cast as wide a net as possible, it was also decided to expand the value chains included in this mapping beyond the scope of the STAR4BBS project. As a result, this report captures impacts evidence on food, feed, and the production of biomass intended for bioenergy. This ensures that the report provides a comprehensive view of available evidence on bio-based value chains and about biomass and feedstocks that can be used in multiple value chains. While other market-based approaches could constitute part of the strategy for transition towards carbon neutrality through financial incentives and regulatory mechanisms, the current systematic mapping is limited to consideration of SCS and labels.

Finally, it should be noted that the focus of our systematic mapping was key academic databases and only a limited selection of grey literature was included, drawing mainly from CAB Abstracts. Evidensia's evidence library contains several reports from ISEAL member organisations that provide information on monitoring and reporting of GHG emissions (e.g., Bonsucro Outcome Report, 2021; Better Cotton Initiative Study of GHG emissions (Morris, 2021); RSPO Impact Report, 2022), and these should be read in conjunction with the current evidence base of largely academic articles.

1.3 Differentiating systematic maps from systematic reviews

A systematic map of research evidence aims to describe and categorise the available evidence relevant to a primary research question, including identifying gaps and limitations in the current evidence base. To create a systematic map search, a protocol is developed and used to search agreed research databases usually agreed by stakeholders. The returned literature is included or rejected through a number of screening steps, and qualifying literature is then coded for analysis. Systematic maps differ from systematic reviews in several important ways. Systematic reviews typically answer a much narrower question and employ statistical analysis to determine effect sizes or "what works".

A systematic map is increasingly used as the first step in a systematic review process. This step is especially relevant for STAR4BBS because the Joint Monitoring System to be developed by this project (see text box) needs to understand what type of evidence is available about the impacts of the specific schemes that will be benchmarked through this system.

STAR4BBS and the Joint Monitoring System:

The **STAR4BBS** project (Sustainability Transition Assessment Rules for Bio-Based Systems) is a Coordination and Support action, which addressed the Horizon Europe call HORIZON-CL6-2021-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-07: International and EU sustainability certification schemes for bio-based systems. Two other projects – **HARMONITOR** (Harmonisation and monitoring platform for certification schemes and labels to advance the sustainability of bio-based systems) and **SUSTCERT4BIOBASED** (Sustainability Certification for Bio-based Systems) were also awarded to address the same call. The three sister projects work together in the implementation of different joint activities. One of them is the development of a Joint Monitoring System, of which the initial proposal, accepted by the EU officials in June 2023, is included in Annex D4.1 of STAR4BBS..

The goal of the three sister projects working together to develop a Joint Monitoring System (JMS) is to reduce confusion, divergences, and mistrust among stakeholders by creating a harmonized, overarching system. This would bring coherence to the space and clarity for policymakers driving the transition to a bioeconomy in the EU. Working together would allow the projects to build on each other's knowledge and experience, subjecting the JMS to a higher level of scrutiny, and maximizing the effective use of resources. The JMS would streamline stakeholder consultations and reduce fatigue while eliminating competition among the three projects and maximizing the synergies and impacts of the results. The creation of a JMS will require greater coordination, but it is believed to be feasible and worthwhile to work together to provide a more comprehensive and detailed tool, covering a wide range of bio-based sectors.

2 Systematic mapping approach and methodology

2.1 Approach

This systematic mapping is a collaborative effort between ISEAL, Oxford Systematic Reviews (OXSREV), Evidensia, and the STAR4BBS consortium. ISEAL has, for over a decade, been investing in understanding and sharing evidence on the impacts of sustainability standards and schemes. It launched Evidensia in 2019 as a public good to share and disseminate relevant credible evidence on the impacts and effectiveness of market-based sustainability approaches and improve uptake of evidence to support decision-making and shape practice. This exercise uses the same approaches and complements past research conducted by Evidensia that has examined the contribution and effectiveness of sustainability systems in achieving sustainability outcomes (see Evidensia's Visual Summaries¹ for more information and previous syntheses.)

As mentioned, this systematic mapping forms one of the background tasks for the STAR4BBS project². The consortium was consulted at various points during the development of the search protocol from conception, shaping the thematic focus of the mapping, and contributing keywords and concepts that were adapted for use in the search strategy.

Stakeholders were consulted as a group formally and informally via 1-2-1s and e-mail exchanges, with formal presentations (14th September 2022; 7th March 2023; 12th June 2023; 27th June 2023).

With this input, a conceptual framework that considers the value chain, tools for change, and enabling practices was developed to indicate how GHG emissions are impacted by each stage of the bioeconomy (Figure 1). This was then translated into a systematic mapping protocol, developed by 18th July 2023 (See Appendix 1a).

¹ <https://www.evidensia.eco/visual-summaries/>

² The STAR4BBS consortium is comprised of 11 institutions and sustainability systems, including: Technische Universität Berlin (TU Berlin) as coordinator, Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea (APRE); Agricultural University of Athens (AUA); Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung und -prüfung (BAM); Better Biomass; ISEAL; NOVA Institut für politische und ökologische Innovation GMBH (NOVA); Roundtable on Sustainable Biomaterials Association (RSB); Ente Italiano di Normazione (UNI); Università degli studi di Roma Unitelma Sapienza (Unitelma Sapienza); Universidade de Santiago de Compostela (USC).

Figure 1: Conceptual framework for the systematic evidence mapping

2.2 Methodology

The systematic map followed the methods set out in The Search Protocol (Appendix Ia) to answer the agreed primary question and four sub-questions. A complete description of the method is available on request, but the main steps are:

1. Scoping and selection of the thematic area;
2. Development of a conceptual framework;
3. Selection of the primary question and development of the sub-questions;
4. Development of The Search Protocol;
5. Return of search results, title and abstract screening, full-text review, and translation of evidence into an extraction sheet (the coding stage);
6. Analysis of the extraction sheet and report writing

Any deviations from the Protocol are noted in the current report.

2.2.1 Defining the search and analysis parameters

A systematic mapping requires the selection of a primary question to use to search for and then screen the literature. This is broken down into its constituent parts in order to prepare search strings, and inclusion and exclusion criteria for the screening stages. Secondary sub-questions are chosen to analyse the screened evidence. For this mapping, the following were chosen:

Primary question:

Do Sustainability Certification Schemes (SCS) and labels, used in the bioeconomy, reduce greenhouse gas emissions?

Sub-question(s):

- a) Are there differences between different sectors of the bioeconomy?
- b) Are there differences between the production of raw materials compared with other parts of the value chain in the bioeconomy?
- c) Are there differences in the primary tools adopted by certification schemes and labels to track GHG emissions?
- d) Where are there significant knowledge gaps in the evidence base in this field of study?

A PICO framework was used to categorise the different aspects of both the primary and secondary questions (Table 1). PICO stands for (study) Population; Intervention; Comparison; and Outcome. It is a common framework initially developed for clinical studies in the Healthcare sector (Cumpston, M. et al., 2019). In order to be included in the review, articles must include information from the population, intervention and outcome sections of the PICO framework (Table 1).

Table 1: Elements of the questions (PICO)

Element	Description
Population	Value chains in the bioeconomy – from producers of primary feedstock to consumers of bio-based products, in any geographic location. Feedstock to include primary agriculture (including horticulture, beekeeping, silk production, etc.), forestry, marine products; biological waste material or residues.
Intervention	Sustainability certification schemes and labels (applicable to the bioeconomy)
Comparator	A different/ absence of sustainability certification scheme(s) or label(s) applicable to the bioeconomy (see further information in the inclusion criteria).
Outcome	Greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (any GHG and combinations of GHG)

The full search strings can be found in Appendix Ia.

2.2.2 Search Strategy and inclusion of grey literature

The search was limited to articles published in or after 2010 and run on three main academic databases – Web of Science, Scopus, and CAB Abstracts.

On the question of grey literature, a rigorous search was carried out on public websites of relevant organisations working in this field but few research reports of relevance were identified as a result. This search however did help inform the development of the Protocol and helped develop subject matter expertise related to how SCS and labels operate. A further call for grey literature was issued during the main search stage of the systematic mapping but inputs were received too late for inclusion in the coding and analysis.

As a result, the evidence mapping is limited to resources from bibliographic databases only (Web of Science, Scopus and CAB Abstracts³). CAB Abstracts is particularly rich in non-academic journal articles, so this was felt to be a reasonable compromise in terms of searching for studies from sources other than academic articles. Notes on potentially relevant reports from stakeholders are included in Appendix Ib and are referred to in section 3.1.9 Evidence Gaps of the current report.

³ CAB Abstracts is an applied life sciences bibliographic database emphasizing agricultural literature. It is published by the Centre for Agriculture and Bioscience International (CABI).

2.2.3 Screening and coding stages

Following the comprehensive search, articles were single-screened, following the inclusion and exclusion criteria below, and coded by four screeners, with consistency checking applied at all stages of the process. Throughout the screening and coding processes, notes were assembled to guide screeners and coders. These notes were included as an Appendix to the Protocol, serving as a living document to ensure consistency and efficiency (available on request).

Table 2: Inclusion criteria

Inclusion Criteria	Description
Population	Value chains in the bioeconomy - from producers of primary feedstock to consumers of bioproducts. Feedstock to include primary agriculture (including horticulture, beekeeping, silk production, etc.), forestry, marine products; biological waste material or residues.
Intervention	Studies examining certification schemes and labels in the bioeconomy
Outcomes	GHG emission (any reported greenhouse gas, combination of gases or reports of unspecified greenhouse gases)
Geographic Scope	Include all geographical regions
Publication Type	Published studies, reports, articles, conference proceedings, and grey literature sources
Date	Studies published after and including 2010

Table 3: Exclusion criteria

Exclusion Criteria	Description
Population	Studies not addressing value chains in the bioeconomy. Biofuels and bioenergy, except where the focus is on the production of the feedstock.
Interventions	Studies not addressing sustainability certification schemes and labels applicable to the bioeconomy.
Outcomes	Studies not addressing GHG emissions
Publication Type/ Study Design	Unpublished materials, personal communications, opinions, editorials, and letters without original research data, systematic reviews, routine monitoring reports, descriptive resources, and modelling studies that examine future scenarios using third-party data.
Date	Studies published before 2010.

Data from the included studies was extracted and summarised in a standardised evidence table (Appendix Ia; PIV). The structure of the extraction sheet is based on the coding and data structure for the Evidensia platform that uses a set typology and taxonomies for systematizing information drawn from relevant research to capture metadata. Additional coding attributes of interest to this study were added to this basic structure and have informed the analysis presented here.

2.2.4 Limitations of the evidence base

The systematic map presented in this report is based on a comprehensive and carefully designed methodology; however, certain limitations inherent in the method and approach may impact the scope and findings of the study.

The decision to restrict the search to articles published in English might have introduced language bias, potentially excluding relevant literature in other languages. While research suggests that a significant portion of academic publications in the field of science is written in English, this limitation could still omit valuable contributions in other languages. Similarly, the decision to restrict grey literature to that which was available from the CAB Abstracts database, has resulted in fewer organisational reports than are potentially relevant. Where these have been noted by stakeholders (Appendix Ib) they have been referred to in

section 3.1.9 Evidence gaps, but they are not included in the current evidence base. Future efforts could consider a more comprehensive treatment of such reports.

The decision not to examine theses databases due to time and resource constraints could also have resulted in the omission of valuable research outputs, particularly from MSc and Doctoral theses from academic institutions.

Despite efforts to ensure consistency in the screening process, the reliance on multiple screeners introduces the possibility of inter-rater variability, potentially affecting the accuracy of study selection. Although Cohen's kappa was used to assess inter-rater agreement, some level of subjectivity might still have influenced the decision-making process.

The systematic map includes studies published from 2010 onwards, potentially excluding important contributions and trends that emerged before this period.

It is important to note that a systematic map, by design, provides a broad overview of the existing literature and identifies key themes, but it does not delve into the depth of analysis provided by a systematic review. As such, while it offers valuable insights, it may not uncover all nuances and specifics of individual studies.

Despite these limitations, the current systematic map offers a comprehensive overview of the available (mainly academic) literature on certification schemes and their implications for GHG emissions within the bioeconomy. The findings should be interpreted considering these limitations to ensure a balanced understanding of the scope and implications of this study.

Discussion

2.3 Part I: Understanding the evidence base

This section includes a full description of the results obtained, showing data for each coded field. All raw data and results can be found in Appendix II (Supplementary Data). Note that figures for the total number of studies do in some cases exceed the number of studies. This is because each incidence of the factor under consideration (for example reference to a particular standard) may have related to more than one region or more than one sector.

2.3.1 Studies in the evidence base

A total of 6286 articles of literature were processed in accordance with the Protocol. Figure 2 shows the systematic filtering process at each stage, which resulted in an evidence mapping of 41 articles (39 journal articles and two conference papers) from 25 journals/other publications. Around three quarters of articles were subscription-only access only (71%), with only just over one quarter of articles (29%) presenting as open access. This has serious implications for non-academic stakeholders who are 'locked out' of important sources of evidence.

Figure 2: Selection and screening of articles and studies reporting inclusion/exclusion

2.3.2 Access to articles

Around three quarters of articles were subscription only access only (71%), with only just over one quarter of articles (29%) presenting as open access (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Accessibility of included articles through subscriptions services or open-access

2.3.3 Location of studies

Figure 4 shows the location of studies, and the number of studies at the country level. Indonesia (n=5) and Italy (n=5) were best represented in the evidence base, followed by Malaysia (n=3), Germany (n=3), United States of America (n=3), and China (n=3).

Figure 4: Location of studies included in the evidence base

2.3.4 Source of studies

Publication type

There are a total of 41 articles of literature that were included at full text of which the vast majority were made up of journal articles (n=39). Data from two conference papers were also included (Table 4).

Table 4: Number of articles by publication type

Publication type	#
Journal Article	39
Conference Paper	2
Total	41

Key journals

A total of 25 journals/resources were represented across the included articles of literature. The *Journal of Cleaner Production* was the most prominent (n=7), followed by *Sustainability* (n=3), and *Forest Ecology and Management* (n=3) (Table 5).

Table 5: Journal/resources with two or more articles

Key Journals	#
Journal of Cleaner Production	7
Sustainability	3
Forest Ecology and Management	3
Scientia Horticulturae	2
Science of the Total Environment	2
Journal of Dairy Science	2
IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science	2
Aquaculture	2

2.3.5 Trends in research volume over time

There is a general trend towards increasing numbers of publications over time, but with spikes in certain years (2019). The earliest article included was published in 2010. The year with the highest number of publications was 2019 with 8 publications. While research in this field has largely increased over the past decade, the number of articles published for the years for 2018 and 2020 present lower

numbers. There is an absence of articles included in the evidence base from 2011-2012 (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Number of articles of literature by date of publication of articles included in the evidence map by (i) individual year and (ii) cumulatively

2.3.6 Certification scheme/label

There were 16 certification schemes/labels reported in the evidence base of which the most common was International Federation of Organic Agriculture Movements (IFOAM) (n=27) (Figure 6). The term ‘organic’ is used somewhat loosely in the literature: there are many different organic standards and authors do not always (or consistently) specify whether the subject is certified as organic, or if it is certified, what that certification is. For the purposes of the current evidence mapping, all studies in organic systems (whether certification has been reported or not) were coded “IFOAM” and results reflect this in Figure AII5. IFOAM studies are organised slightly differently in the discussion section.

Figure 6: Number of studies addressing GHG emissions across certification scheme/label (n=>3) grouped by geographic region as defined by the United Nations Statistical Division

The other certification schemes that reported >1 instance is Forest Stewardship Council (FSC) (n=5), Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil (RSPO) (n=4), VIVA (n=2), USDA National Organic Program (n=2), and Naturland (n=2). The remaining 10 certification schemes/labels reported evidence from a single study: Sweden’s organic certifier (KRAV), Standard for Sustainable Cattle Production Systems, Rainforest Alliance (RA), Malaysia Sustainable Palm Oil Standard (MSPO), Label Rouge, Green Food Program (China), Danish Crown’s sustainability certification scheme, Aquaculture Stewardship Council (ASC), China Organic Agricultural Product Standard, and Environmentally-Friendly Agricultural Products Certification standard (Republic of Korea). IFOAM studies appeared across 9 regions in the evidence base with the greatest instances coming from Western Europe (n=5), Southern Europe (n=5), Northern America (n=4), and Southeastern Asia (n=3). FSC certification was reported from 4 regions, and RSPO certification only from Southeastern Asia (n=4).

Geographic regions followed the grouping by the United Nations Statistical Division (United Nations, 1999).

2.3.7 Sector

The number of studies addressing GHG emissions was highest for the sector of agriculture, followed by forestry and livestock (Figure 7). Although literature on

other sectors of interest to the project (textiles, furniture, bio-based chemicals, and construction) (STAR4BBS, 2023b) was captured in the original search, these did not meet the inclusion criteria outlined above.

Within the agricultural sector the geographic region of Southeast Asia comprises 33% (n=9) of studies followed by Southern Europe (n=4) Eastern Asia, (n=4), and South America (n=4). Forestry is best represented by Middle Africa (n=3); and Livestock by Western Europe (n=3) (Figure 7). Processed food (n=4) is represented in two studies from both Western Europe and Southern Europe; and Fish - Aquaculture (n=4) is represented in two studies from both Western Europe and Southeastern Asia. There is one study examining textiles/garments (from Western Asia).

Figure 7: Number of studies addressing GHG emissions across sectors grouped by geographic region as defined by the United Nations Statistical Division

2.3.8 Feedstock/product

Data were reported for 32 feedstocks/products, of which timber products, palm oil, rice and dairy products had the highest number of studies. Most products were reported in a single study each.

Studies examining timber products are predominantly from Middle Africa (n=3) and Central America (n=2) with single studies from South America (n=1) and Southeastern Asia (n=1). Palm oil studies are exclusively from Southeastern Asia (n=6). Rice production is mostly covered by Eastern (n=3) and Southeastern (n=2) Asia with three studies coming from Western Europe (n=1), Southern Europe (n=1), and Northern America (n=1). Dairy product studies are primarily from Western Europe (n=4) with one from Northern America (n=1) and another from Northern Europe (n=1) (Figure 8). Studies reporting on pork meat (n=3) are situated in Western Europe (n=2) and Northern Europe (n=1). There are two studies reporting evidence for each of the following feedstocks/products: wine, wheat, blueberries,

finfish, beef meat, and agriculture products (multiple); and one study reporting evidence for: sugar beet, soy shrimps, potato, peas, onions, oats, kale, garment, cucumber, cocoa, catfish, beans, cereals, fresh fruits and vegetables, nuts and oilseeds, sugar, poultry meat, livestock animals, eggs, and food products (unspecified).

Figure 8: Number of studies addressing GHG emissions (n=>3) across feedstock/product grouped by geographic region as defined by the United Nations Statistical Division

2.3.9 Stage of value chain

The production phase had the largest number of studies, followed by processing, with disposal being the least represented life cycle stage. Disposal is the least represented life cycle stage in the evidence base. Studies in the production stage and processing stage were primarily from the agricultural sectors (n=23 and n=6 respectively).

Evidence for the production phase comes from 11 regions with Southeastern Asia (n=10) as the most prominent, followed by Southern Europe (n=6), Western Europe (n=5), and South America (n=5). Evidence for Southeastern Asia is also most prominent for the processing phase (n=4). For manufacturing singular instances of GHG impact evidence reported across 4 regions. Use phase evidence comes from Western Europe (n=2), Eastern Asia (n=1), and Western Asia (n=1). The Disposal stage presents single studies from Western Europe (n=1), Eastern Asia (n=1), and Western Asia (n=1).

Figure 9: Number of studies addressing GHG emissions across certification scheme/label grouped by geographic region as defined by the United Nations Statistics Division

Studies in the production stage and processing stage were primarily from the agricultural sector (n=23 and n=6 respectively). Use phase, manufacturing, and disposal are mixed across agriculture, processed food, and textiles. In addition, the use phase has evidence for fish and livestock (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Number of studies addressing GHG emissions across certification scheme/label grouped by sector

2.3.10 Study design

Of the 41 studies, all except one adopted quantitative study designs to draw conclusions about impact and only one was qualitative. Of the 40 quantitative studies only one had data collected before and after the intervention, whilst all others had data collected post-intervention. Twenty nine had matched controls, six had no controls, and four had a control that was not matched. This indicates a

relatively robust set of studies based on largely quantitative study designs, with most including some form of counterfactual analysis.

2.3.11 Impact of certification/labels on GHG emissions

As noted earlier, a systematic mapping effort mainly focusses on a review of the evidence base and not the conclusions of the evidence itself. Nonetheless, we have attempted to provide a brief review of relevant articles to provide readers with a flavour of what the studies say on the question of SCS and labels' impact on GHG emissions.

Of the 41 articles identified through the systematic search, clear directionality of impact (i.e. whether the study design and results found a clear causal link between the intervention (SCS or label) and outcome (the reduction of GHG emissions)) was concluded only in 31 articles whereas for 10, the authors were not able to establish clear directionality. This section draws on this body of literature and presents some insights.

Table 6: Articles that indicate a positive or negative impact to GHG emissions

Directionality	#
No	11
Yes	30

Of the 31 articles, 25 reported positive performance of the certified subjects when compared with non-certified or conventional systems (i.e., lower emissions), and 6 demonstrated a negative performance.

For the 11 articles that showed no directionality, there was either no non-certified comparator, or researchers were not able to demonstrate a clear difference in emissions between certified and non-certified subjects. At least one study contained too much variability across results to draw a general conclusion, while another suggested uncertainty over climate impact data as it was estimated using a separate model.

2.3.12 Sustainable Development Goal focus

There were three sustainable development goals (SDG's) identified across the evidence base: SDG 13 (Climate Action) SDG 12 (Responsible Production & Consumption), and SDG 14 (Life Below Water) (Figure 11). Climate action was represented across 10 regions presenting most evidence for SDG 13 from Southeastern Asia (n=11), followed by Western (n=6) and Southern Europe (n=6). Evidence for Responsible Production & Consumption was found across 9 regions and was also best represented in Southeastern Asia (n=4). Life Below Water was found for one study in Western Europe only.

Figure 11: Number of studies addressing GHG emissions across sustainable development goals by region as defined by the United Nations Statistical Division.

A total of 32 feedstocks/products were represented across the three SDGs in the evidence base with those with evidence $n \geq 3$ for Climate Action including Rice ($n=7$), Dairy products ($n=6$), Palm Oil ($n=5$), Timber products ($n=5$), and pork meat ($n=3$). Responsible Production & Consumption only has evidence for one feedstocks/product with $n \geq 3$ which is Palm Oil (Figure 12).

Figure 12: Number of studies addressing GHG emissions across sustainable development goals by feedstock/product ($n > 3$)

2.3.13 Duration of studies

Studies that reported their duration were found to have lasted largely less than or equal to 1 year ($n=11$). Medium term studies (1-3 years) presented evidence from 9 studies, and longer-term studies (greater than 3 years) comprised just 4 studies. Almost half of the studies ($n=15$) did not report their length (Figure 13).

Figure 13: Length of studies in months

2.3.14 Risk of bias of the evidence base

The risk of bias assessment of the systematic map's evidence base revealed a spectrum of bias risk among the included articles (Figure 14). While there are studies with low risk of bias, according to the critical appraisal criteria (adapted from the Joanna Briggs Institute), a significant portion of the evidence base exhibits medium- to high- bias risk. These findings highlight the need for a discerning approach when using this evidence base to inform research and decision-making. The evidence mapping enables policymakers and practitioners to filter out studies of high risk of bias in favour of studies with a low risk of bias when using the evidence base to understand the implications of certification on GHG emissions. Ultimately, promoting robust research practices and transparency in conducting and reporting primary research remains important for ensuring the credibility of evidence for decision making.

Only four out of the 41 articles coded in the evidence base scored in the lowest risk of bias considering (i) accountability of any missing data; (ii) the study subjects and setting being described in detail; (iii) the intervention(s) described including details of certification timing, and duration; (iv) a clear account of the statistical/analytical methods used to compare groups for all GHG outcome(s); and (v) availability of all raw data (Figure 14), adapted from the Joanna Briggs Institute . A further five articles placed in the low/medium risk of bias category. The majority of articles scored in medium risk of bias (n=28). Three articles scored in medium/high risk of bias and two articles scored in high risk (Figure 14).

Figure 14: Risk of bias in the evidence base

2.3.15 Evidence gaps

Only 16 certification schemes and labels were captured for the evidence mapping, of which only IFOAM, FSC and RSPO had more than three studies. There is a clear need for more research on GHG emissions linked to other schemes.

Of the 15 sectors listed in Evidensia’s library, only six are represented in the evidence base, and of these only Agriculture, Forestry, Livestock, Processed Food, and Fish (aquaculture) have more than three studies dealing with GHG emissions. There is a need for more primary research in these missing or under-reported sectors.

There is a dearth of literature in academic journals on the impact of SCS and labels on GHG emissions in six of the products that have historically formed a large part of the sustainability certification literature, namely cocoa, bananas, tea, coffee, cotton, sugarcane. It should be noted that Evidensia’s evidence library contains several Reports from member organisations that provide information on monitoring and reporting of GHG emissions (e.g., Bonsucro Outcome Report, 2021, Better Cotton Initiative Study of GHG emissions (Morris, 2021), RSPO Impact Report, 2022), and these should be read in conjunction with the current evidence base of largely academic articles.

In terms of the value chain, only the production stage is well represented; disposal and use phase are particularly poorly represented in the evidence base. The evidence base contains few studies that report the contribution of individual GHGs, even where the individual gases have been listed in the article. These are mainly converted to carbon dioxide equivalent measurements, and while this is not problematic if this is clearly understood, there is a danger of comparing different gases or combinations of gases together in a manner that may lead to errors in interpretation, for example, the impact of a certification scheme on methane emissions reduction.

The geographical focus of studies included in the evidence base shows some possibly unexpected gaps. Comparing the spread of studies in the current

evidence base with the geographic representation of studies in the Evidensia library⁴, it is clear that there are evidence gaps for South and East Africa, Central America, India, Russia and the Philippines.

⁴ <https://www.evidensia.eco/work-with-evidence/geo-map/>

2.4 Part II Evidence analysis of the effects of SCS and labels on GHG emissions reductions

Studies included in the evidence base are grouped by sector and discussed under specific certification schemes and labels below. Each section begins with a brief assessment of scheme criteria or principles relating to GHG emissions and then includes a synthesis of evidence from the evidence base of impact of each certification / label.

2.4.1 Organic agriculture

This section discusses studies involving the International Federation of Organic Agriculture Movements (IFOAM), VIVA, Naturland, Green Food Program (China), Label Rouge, USDA Organic, the Danish Crown's Sustainability Certification Scheme, Sweden's organic certifier (KRAV), the Environmentally friendly Agricultural Products Certification (EFAPC) standard (Republic of Korea), the China Organic Agricultural Product Standard. A number of studies did not specify their specific certification, or the certification status was unclear. As we cannot confidently exclude these articles, they have been included under the umbrella of "unspecified organic".

It should be noted while reading this section that 1) many sustainability certifications include organic as part of their standard, and 2) many agricultural farms hold multiple certifications (certified organic + another scheme). It is therefore difficult in reality to discern causality between what effects change and one should be cautious about extrapolating the results listed below.

International Federation of Organic Agriculture Movements (IFOAM)

The International Federation of Organic Agriculture Movements (IFOAM) is a membership organization covering over 100 countries. IFOAM is dedicated to promoting the uptake of organic agriculture and associated approaches (certified and non-certified); encouraging the progression of organic operations from good practice to best practice; and increasing the number of agriculture operations that are integrating organic principles and methods (IFOAM, 2023). It does so through a family of standards that many other certifications derive their guidelines from.

Given IFOAM's prominence in promoting organic practices, and the ambiguity expressed in many of the articles, IFOAM has been used as an umbrella term to code all papers including "organic" subjects, unless another certification scheme has been explicitly provided. Articles that have provided evidence of certification with a named organic scheme are discussed under separate headings below, while articles which have not specified the organic scheme have been discussed under "Unspecified Organic". Articles that report on 'organic' systems but do not provide any explicit evidence of a certification scheme are not further discussed (Lazzerini et al. 2014; Treu, et al. 2017; Fernandes Guareschui et al. 2019; Yuttitham, 2019; Bos et al. 2021; Hermanto et al. 2021; Jirapornvaree et al. 2021; Viana et al. 2022; Bux et al. 2022; Lambotte et al. 2023), though they are coded "IFOAM" as part of the evidence mapping.

VIVA

The VIVA certification program “Sustainability in viticulture in Italy” is a program by the Italian Ministry of Environment and Energy Security, which since 2011 has been promoting the sustainability of the Italian wine sector. (VIVA, 2022a). The standard is organised around four “indicator categories”: “Air”, “Water”, “Vineyard” and “Territory”. (VIVA, 2022b) Two papers (Borsato et al., 2020; Casolani et al., 2023) reported on the impacts of VIVA certification on GHG emissions. Both specifically focused on the agronomical management practices detailed under the “Vineyard” indicator category.

Borsato et al. (2020) compared two vineyards within the same case study farm in Italy, where conventional and organic viticulture⁵ practices were applied. VIVA certification methods were used to calculate the GHG emissions factor (based on methane, nitrous oxide and carbon dioxide estimates) for pesticides and fertiliser applications, as well as for fuel consumption. There is a high statistical difference between organic and conventional practice for the application of fertilisers and pesticides, though GHG emissions from field work operations (e.g., soil cultivation, canopy management, irrigation, and plant protection) are not statistically different between organic and conventional management.

Casolani et al. (2023) examined production, manufacture and processing stages of 45 certified wines in Italy. The authors reported great variability in the results of GHG emissions and observed that there was therefore opportunity for improvement in many companies.

Naturland and Bioland

Naturland is a German association for organic farming created in 1982, with the mission of spreading organic certification worldwide. (Naturland, 2023a). Naturland have several standards covering 13 environmental and social areas (Naturland, 2023b). Two papers (Jonell et al., 2015; Kiefer et al., 2014) are included in the evidence base. The first examines the impact of Naturland’s Aquaculture Standards (specific standards under which are unspecified), while the second discusses impacts where subjects certified under Naturland’s Production Standards (again, unspecified) formed part of the study sample. The sample in Kiefer et al also included organic farms that followed the guidelines of the Bioland farming association, an organic movement also active in Germany (Bioland, 2023).

Jonell et al. (2015) reported on 21 organic and 20 non-organic mangrove shrimp farms in Vietnam. The emissions of GHG per ton of shrimp produced were substantial for both groups, and almost solely caused by the release of carbon during mangrove land transformation. Organic farms emitted less GHGs than non-organic farms.

⁵ Viticulture refers to the cultivation of grapevines.

Kiefer et al. (2014) reported on 81 nonrepresentative⁶ dairy farms in southern Germany. The study reported that organic farms produced Product Carbon Footprints (PCF) that were significantly higher than those produced by conventional farms. PCF values for both types of farms in this study were markedly higher than the respective results of other, similar, studies. A PCF communicates the quantity of GHG emissions that are produced or consumed during the life cycle of a product.

Green Food Program (China)

The Green Good Certified (GFC) is a Chinese eco-certification scheme for food, that has been active since the 1980s (Paull, 2008). The Green Food Development Center provides a certification label that focuses on sustainable agricultural practices, reduced pesticide use, and environmental criteria that aims to minimise the environmental impact of food production (Paull, 2008). One paper in the evidence base (Wang et al., 2017) looks at the impact of GFC certification.

Wang et al. (2017) used life cycle assessment to evaluate environmental impacts (including global warming potential, measured as carbon dioxide-equivalents for carbon dioxide, methane and nitrous oxide) of GFC cucumber cultivated under a greenhouse system in Beijing, China relative to conventional cultivation. The environmental index⁷ of the 13 GFC cucumber farms was reported to be higher than that of the 30 non-certified farms, largely due to higher fertiliser use.

Label Rouge

Label Rouge is a quality-assurance packaging label created by the French Ministry of Agriculture that can be applied to food and non-food agricultural products of any geographical origin. Attainment of the label is based on sensorial perception; production conditions; the perception of product conditions; presentation and service elements (Label Rouge, 2016). One study including Label Rouge (Teixeira et al., 2013) is included in the evidence base. It compares and reports GHG emissions in nine pork-based pâtés from Label Rouge, organic, conventional, and Bleu-Blanc-Cœur (a special finishing technique) systems. The study covers all stages of the products' lives, from production to disposal.

The authors report that Label Rouge pâtés cause higher emissions than conventional pâtés, despite providing less calories and more protein. The organic pâté was between the conventional and Bleu-Blanc-Cœur systems on the calories scale and had a carbon footprint similar to Label Rouge. GHG emissions were reported as lower for conventional pork pâtés than for organic pork pâtés, as an indirect consequence of the lower productivity of swine feed ingredients. The authors noted that the study raised interesting methodological points that should

⁶ Not representative of all farms in southern Germany.

⁷ The index is made up of eight environmental impact categories: global warming potential, energy depletion (ED), water depletion, acidification potential, aquatic eutrophication (AEU), human toxicity (HT), aquatic eco-toxicity (AET), and soil eco-toxicity (SET).

be addressed for life cycle analysis in the future, to standardise the methodology and promote interstudy comparability.

USDA Organic

The United States Department of Agriculture (USDA) created the national standard for organic production (USDA Organic) under the Food, Agriculture, Conservation, and Trade Act of 1990. The standard covers all agricultural systems and defines organic food as that “produced without using most conventional pesticides; fertilisers made with synthetic ingredients or sewage sludge; bioengineering; or ionizing radiation” (Congress, U.S. 1990). The evidence mapping includes two articles (Liang et al., 2017; McGee, 2014) that discuss the impacts of the USDA Organic Program.

Liang et al. (2017) used a partial life cycle assessment approach to estimate the effect of different feeding strategies and associated crop production on GHG emissions from Wisconsin certified organic dairy farms. The authors reported that higher levels of milk production played a significant role in reducing GHG emissions per metric tonne of energy-corrected milk (ECM). The authors also reported that increasing the proportion of soybean in cattle diet was linked to an increase in GHG emissions per metric tonne of ECM. However, including soybean in the crop rotation was reported to decrease nitrous oxide emissions due to lower applications of organically approved nitrogen fertility inputs. In addition, higher levels of soybean in the diet, which replaced corn grain, were reported to reduce enteric methane emissions per metric tonne of ECM because of higher dietary fat content. This dietary change was found to be beneficial for lowering methane emissions. Shifting from a grain-based diet to a more pasture-based one was reported to lead to a decrease in milk production. This reduction in milk yield was found to result in substantially higher emissions per metric tonne of ECM. Therefore, a higher reliance on pasture at the expense of grain was associated with increased GHG emissions.

McGee (2014) reported that the rise of certified organic production of agricultural products in the United States is not correlated with a decline in GHG emissions, and instead a positive association between certified organic farming and overall agricultural GHG emissions are reported. The author’s analysis indicates that an increase in certified organic farmland from 2000 to 2008 is positively correlated with GHG emissions from agricultural production. This suggests that organic farming practices are currently contributing to an increase in emissions of GHG. McGee (2014) also reports that organic farming may lead to more GHG emissions due to lower yields and reliance on machinery. The results also suggest that certain organic crops might produce more GHG compared to their conventional counterparts. While the study’s findings do not support a direct link between organic farming and lower GHG emissions, they acknowledge the possibility that organic agriculture could affect different types of GHG emissions in complex ways.

Danish Crown’s Sustainability Certification Scheme

One study (Olsen et al., 2023) is included in the evidence mapping that discusses organic production under the Danish Crown Sustainability Certification Scheme. However, there is a lack of contextual information for this scheme, making it difficult to ascertain its parameters. This is important to note as an overarching certification scheme no longer exists at Danish Crown.

Using Denmark as a case study, Olsen et al. (2023) reported on CO₂ impacts of five different pig production systems (1. Standard pig production (465 herds), 2. Animal welfare (1 herd), 3. Raised without antibiotics (18 herds), 4. Free range (8 herds), 5. Organic (16 herds)) all certified as part of Danish Crown's sustainability certification scheme. Systems 1, 2, and 3 were indoor year-round, with 4 and 5 being partially outdoors. The authors reported that the Organic system had the highest impact per kg, followed by Free range, then the three indoor systems had the lowest impacts per kg.

Sweden's organic certifier (KRAV)

Krav is a prominent Swedish eco-label for organically produced food, established in 1985. Krav-labelled food is produced without artificial chemical pesticides and without artificial fertiliser (Krav, 2023). One study (Aggestam & Buick, 2017) was found in the evidence mapping that included Krav certification.

Aggestam & Buick (2017) report that certified organic milk production in Sweden leads to a reduction in emissions associated with road-related transport; however, this reduction is outweighed by the increase in emissions resulting from farmyard vehicles used for producing feed on the farm.

Environmentally Friendly Agricultural Products Certification (EFAPC) standard (Republic of Korea)

EFAPC is a certification from the government of the Republic of Korea. One article (Kim et al., 2018) discussing EFAPC was included in the evidence mapping. In this, EFAPC certified farms adhered to fertiliser ingredient content as recommended by the administrator of Rural Development (Kim et al. 2018).

Kim et al. (2018) examined the implications of the various certification systems for rice farming, including organic farming, non-pesticide farming, and low-pesticide farming. They evaluated GHG emissions of rice farms in the Republic of Korea certified by the EFAPC standard and compared these with other international rice produced to organic standards in the USA and the EU. The environmental impacts of rice farming were highest in the U.S., followed in descending order by the EU, Korea's conventional, low-pesticide, non-pesticide, and organic farming practices.

China Organic Agricultural Product Standard

The China Organic Standard GB/T 19630-2019 enables organically produced raw agricultural products to be commercialized as organic in mainland China and Hong Kong (ECOCERT, 2023). There is one paper (Zhen et al., 2023) in the evidence mapping that discusses the standard.

Zhen et al. (2023) compared the GHG emissions of organic (certified with the China Organic Agricultural Product Standard) rice-fish co-culture, and conventional rice value chains (including cultivation, processing, transportation, cooking, and waste disposal). The authors reported that organic rice had the highest carbon input, output, and net GHG emissions in the farming system. Methane contributed more than 60% of the total GHG emissions of the three rice farming systems. Post-harvest systems, including processing, waste disposal, and transportation, contributed little to the GHG emissions of the three rice value chains. Organic rice had higher GHG emissions than rice-fish co-culture and conventional rice along the value chain, mainly from the farming system due to higher organic material inputs.

Unspecified Organic

Eight papers included reference to certification but did not specify, or did not include enough information about certification of the subjects to exclude them. They have been included here under the umbrella of “unspecified organic”.

Cordes et al. (2016) reported nitrous oxide emissions (from organic nitrogen fertilisers) in production and processing of five blueberry orchards in Chile. Agricultural factors such as fertilisers, pesticides, fossil fuels, electricity, materials, machinery, and direct land use change were included in the analysis of carbon footprint. The authors note that the variability in the results suggests that the production practices have important effects on the carbon footprint and stress the importance of reporting separately the GHG emissions from land-use change.

Vaglia et al. (2022) reported GHG emissions from 10 farms certified as part of the Organic Rice Network in Italy. Environmental impact values are affected by a wide range of variations, depending on the farmer’s choices (water management, weed control strategy, and nutrients and organic matter management plans). Specifically, impact categories affected by energy and fossil fuels consumption in organic rice are reported to have a positive effect and reduce the relative contribution of fertiliser on the total impact.

Baydar et al. (2015) assessed environmental impacts (including global warming) of Eco T-shirts produced in Turkey. The Eco T-shirts are made from organically grown cotton and processed with a green dyeing recipe and are compared with environmental impacts of conventional T-shirts using a life cycle assessment methodology. The authors conclude that Eco T-shirts have lower impact potentials across all inspected categories and that the global warming potential is the largest environmental impact for both conventional and Eco T-shirts with the main impact coming from use phase, followed by cultivation, and harvesting and fabric processing phases.

Biermann et al. (2019) used Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology to compare the environmental impacts of conventional and organic common carp certified under European Commission Regulation (EC) No 710/2009 raised in traditional pond aquaculture in Germany. The authors note that the environmental

superiority of one production method over the other depends on the impact category analyzed and there is, therefore, no clear impact of organic certification in isolation.

Kontopoulou et al. (2015) studied the impacts of organic vs. conventional farming practices on nitrous oxide emissions in a field experiment in west Greece. The authors reported that organic farming resulted in insignificantly lower emissions than conventional farming in terms of the overall Global Warming Potential of the farming treatments.

Using highbush blueberry as a target crop, Montalba et al. (2019) analyzed environmental impacts comparing three different types of management in south-central Chile: conventional orchards, orchards with organic management based on input substitution, and orchards with organic management based on agroecological principles. Four orchards for each type of management were measured. GHG emissions of conventional orchards were higher than emissions of both organic regimes. Most GHG emissions in conventional orchards were originated by these farms' external inputs for soil management and pest control. There were no differences among management regimes in their impacts in GHG emissions owing to machinery and irrigation management.

Qin et al. (2010) reported on the impacts of different irrigation methods and cropping systems on GHG emissions in rice paddies, particularly comparing organic and conventional approaches. The study demonstrates that the choice of irrigation method and cropping system significantly affects GHG emissions and their potential impact on radiative forcing in rice paddies. The impact of organic versus conventional systems depends on the specific water regime used and the balance between methane and nitrous oxide emissions.

Bandanaa et al. (2021) compared 398 cocoa farmers in Ghana, of which 71 were organic, and 327 conventional. The authors reported that the organic farming system was better in terms of GHG emission reduction and improvement in air quality compared with non-organic farms. Some subjects were noted as being Rainforest Alliance certified as a pre-requisite for entry into their specific farming groups, however the analysis does not attempt to attribute specific benefits to the Rainforest Alliance certification itself.

2.4.2 Palm oil

The evidence mapping captured articles discussing the impact of the Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil (RSPO) and the Malaysia Sustainable Palm Oil (MSPO) Standard.

The Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil (RSPO)

RSPO were founded in 2004 to address the global call for sustainably produced palm oil. Their certification includes a set of environmental and social criteria that help minimise the negative impact of palm oil production on the local

environment, wildlife and communities (RSPO, 2023a). Three papers (Schmidt & De Rosa, 2020; De Rosa et al., 2022; Hilmi & Utami, 2021) were included in the evidence mapping that involve RSPO certification.

Evidence from two of the three articles that examine the impact of RSPO certification on GHG emissions (carbon dioxide, methane, and nitrous oxide expressed as CO₂ equivalent) indicated that two certified plantations in Indonesia produced less GHG emissions than non-certified Palm Oil plantations across Indonesia and Malaysia (non-certified data averaged across palm oil produced across Indonesia & Malaysia) (Schmidt & De Rosa, 2020; De Rosa et al. 2022). The datasets for certified and non-certified palm oil in both of these papers are the same. All GHG emission results from these papers are modelled from selected key performance indicators for oil palm cultivation (e.g., planted area, soil type, and application of nutrients and fertilisers).

In both papers, the authors report that RSPO certification has a positive impact on reducing GHG emissions in palm oil production, primarily through better land use practices, use of a peat soil-free supply base, and improved management of various stages of the production process.

Schmidt & De Rosa (2020) report a 35% reduction in GHG emissions compared to non-certified palm oil and primarily attribute this reduction to higher yields generated per unit of land. De Rosa et al. (2022) reports a reduction of GHG emissions of 49-58% for certified palm oil from Hanau and Sungai Rungau facilities (Indonesia) compared against the average non-certified palm oil across Indonesia & Malaysia.

In the crop cultivation stage, avoiding the use of tropical peatland is reported as a key factor in reducing the GHG emissions (De Rosa et al. 2022). During the manufacturing stage, De Rosa et al. (2022) reported lower contributions of GHG emissions for one RSPO certified oil palm production plant due to biogas capture facilities, compared with average certified production. However, higher than average methane production is reported for the other RSPO certified oil palm production plant due to the absence of biogas capture facilities. The use of residues from the palm oil process are also indicated to be useful in the production of electricity, which when combined with a biogas capture facility, avoids further GHG emissions from the palm oil creation process. Schmidt & De Rosa (2020) further suggest, through modelling, that the by-products of palm oil cultivation and production reduce GHGs through use as animal feed, while De Rosa et al. (2022) model a reduction when used in the production of biodiesel. No difference was detected between certified and non-certified palm oil refining (Schmidt & De Rosa, 2020)

In contrast to the results from Schmidt & De Rosa (2020) and De Rosa et al. (2022), Hilmi & Utami (2021), reported that RSPO certification had no significant effect on the amount of CO₂ emissions produced when compared against non-certified palm oil production.

The results reported from these three articles, highlight the fact that studies using the differences in methods and variables used to model GHG emissions for the production of palm oil and the range of effect variables that are considered in different models.

MSPO

The Malaysian Sustainable Palm Oil (MSPO) Certification Scheme is the national scheme in Malaysia for oil palm plantations, independent and organized smallholdings, and palm oil processing facilities to be certified against the requirements of the MSPO Standards (MSPO, 2023). One study (Bok et al., 2022) examined the environmental life cycle assessment and life cycle costing on the uncertified and MSPO-certified fresh fruit bunches production among independent smallholders to determine the impacts of MSPO implementation. They report lower environmental impact with certified smallholders. The reduction of GHG emissions is attributed to fertilizer production and diesel consumption (processing) in machinery in Malaysia. The incorporation of organic fertilizers emerges as an effective strategy for mitigating the overall environmental footprint associated with the cultivation practices of fresh fruit bunches.

2.4.3 Forestry

Where Forestry was concerned, the evidence mapping only captured articles discussing the Forest Stewardship Council (FSC).

Forest Stewardship Council (FSC)

FSC's certification system verifies sustainable sourcing of forest products and ecosystem services at every step of the value chain, from forest to consumer. It is underpinned by FSC's sustainable forestry standards (FSC, 2023b).

Five papers presented data for GHG emissions in FSC-certified forests or forest tracts compared with non-certified forests. Of these, three (Umunay et al., 2019; Ellis et al., 2019; Goodman et al., 2019) reported no impact of certification on GHG emissions and two (Griscom et al., 2014; Armenta-Montero et al., 2020) reported a positive impact for some forestry operations associated with FSC certification.

Umunay et al (2019) assessed reduced-impact logging for carbon emissions reductions (RIL-C) in 23 commercial forest concessions in the Congo Basin (nine concessions in Gabon, eight in the Democratic Republic of the Congo, and six in the Republic of the Congo). The concessions were selected to cover a wide range of management categories, logging practices, and pre-logging biomass carbon stocks, that compared carbon dioxide emissions in six FSC-certified concessions with 17 non-certified concessions (either with registered management plans, or with only temporary logging permits). Logging emissions were dominated by damage caused by road and log landing construction (hauling) and felling (including carbon in extracted logs). Although carbon emissions per cubic metre of timber harvested differed between countries, they did not differ significantly between FSC-certified and non-certified concessions. The authors note that

although logging roads are easily monitored with remote sensing or by FSC auditors in the field, it is harder to track felling emissions from abandoned logs and poor bucking (cutting felled trees into logs), both of which are tracked with the RIL-C methodology⁸. They recommend that some form of this methodology be incorporated into national standards to quantify logging emissions.

Ellis et al. (2019) also reported that FSC certification was not associated with any difference in carbon emissions from selective logging in RIL-C practices in community forests on the Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico. The authors also note that adoption of RIL-C practices by all community forestry in the region would contribute substantially to the Mexican forest sector's efforts to mitigate climate change.

Goodman et al. (2019) looked at carbon emissions from felling, skidding, and hauling in concessions in Peru, comparing five FSC-certified concessions where workers were trained in reduced-impact logging (RIL) and four non-certified concessions where workers were not trained in RIL. Supporting earlier studies, the authors reported that concessions practicing RIL harvested at lower intensities and consequently had lower emissions per ha, however, there was no difference in carbon emissions between certified and non-certified concessions once logging intensity was taken into account.

Griscom et al. (2014) compared concessions certified by FSC (n = 3), in East Kalimantan, Indonesia with non-certified concessions (n = 6). They found that although certified concessions did not have lower overall carbon dioxide emissions from logging, they did have lower emissions from one type of logging impact – skidding. An important factor noted by the authors was that FSC criteria and indicators, and associated RIL practices, were not specifically designed to achieve overall emissions reductions. They recommended that if tropical forest certification is to be linked with carbon emissions reductions, certification standards need to explicitly require RIL-C practices.

Armenta-Montero et al. (2020) reported on selective logging operations in two forestry communities, one of which was FSC-certified and incorporated RIL, in the Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico. There were lower emissions and damage from felling and skidding in the FSC certified concession.

2.4.4 Cattle production

This section includes one article that discusses sustainable cattle production under the Sustainable Agriculture Network (SAN) and Rainforest Alliance

Standard for Sustainable Cattle Production Systems

⁸ The Reduced Impact Logging for carbon emission reductions (RIL-C) protocol was developed to measure emissions from selective logging in Indonesia by its main source (either felling, skidding, or hauling), and to estimate the possible emissions reductions from adoption of improved logging practices. (Umunay et al., 2019)

The Standard for Sustainable Cattle Production Systems, developed by the Sustainable Agriculture Network (SAN) and Rainforest Alliance, only applies to farms where cattle have access to pasture. It includes the following principles: integrated management systems, sustainable pasture management, animal welfare and carbon-footprint reduction. One study (Bogaerts et al., 2017) related to the standard was included in the evidence mapping.

Bogaerts et al. (2017) compared GHG emissions from beef farms certified by the SAN Standard for sustainable cattle production systems against emissions from farms operating under one of four different programs ((Novo Campo Project (Instituto Centro de Vida), Rondonia Intensification Program (Imaflora, Vida Verde, Marfrig Global Foods), Silvipastoral Program (Instituto de Conservação e Desenvolvimento Sustentavel do Amazonas), and Pecuaría Verde Program (Sindicato Rural de Produtores Rurais de Paragomina)). In the study 19 farmers were participating in a sustainability or certification program and 21 farmers were not. The single SAN-certified farm had a per kilogram GHG emissions output substantially lower than the averages of other groups of farms, although the authors note that there were individual farms which had lower emissions. As noted above, Rainforest Alliance administers the SAN scheme, but the data do not support an assessment of the effects of Rainforest Alliance on GHG emissions.

2.4.5 Aquaculture

Like Forestry and Cattle Production, Aquaculture is only represented by one certification: Aquaculture Stewardship Council (ASC) certification.

Aquaculture Stewardship Council (ASC)

The Aquaculture Stewardship Council (ASC) was launched in 2010 with the goal of making aquaculture more sustainable. The ASC certification validated seafood and farm's adherence to their strict underpinning standards (ASC, 2023). One study (Nhu et al., 2016) discussed ASC certification.

Nhu et al. (2016) reported that GHG emissions for an ASC-certified farm in Vietnam were generally lower than a non-certified farm. This was attributed to the fact that Pangasius feed (consisting of fishmeal and fish oil) is generally restricted in ASC certified Pangasius farming.

3 Conclusions

There are large differences in the volume of evidence for different sectors and products of the bioeconomy. Agriculture is the only sector that has enough studies to allow evidence-informed decision-making about the impact of SCS and labels on GHG emissions at the production stage (see figure 10). In fact, even for this sector, the dominance of evidence pertaining to organic systems (not all of which are delineated by named certification schemes) means that caution should be applied in interpreting the evidence. Further, the mapping is dominated by evidence from South-East Asia and parts of Europe, so caution must be applied to generalising the results to other regions and countries.

Most stages of the value chain are not well represented: the production stage dominates the evidence base. Again, caution should be applied to generalising from evidence for the production stage to other phases in the value chain. The geographical limitations discussed above are equally valid for consideration of stages of the value chain.

The evidence base shows significant knowledge gaps in terms of specific certification schemes and labels, most sectors and products, and most parts of the life cycle. These evidence gaps represent a research opportunity to advance not only knowledge of impacts of certification on GHG emissions, but also to address lacunae in the certification schemes and labels themselves, particularly in respect of measuring and monitoring.

Finally, it is unclear how specifically many schemes target GHG reduction as an outcome of interest, though they do focus on many important enabling conditions. Similarly, many schemes have GHG calculators (RSPO; MSPO; Bonsucro) that they require certified entities to use to track and manage emissions. This suggests that emissions are being incorporated as a key concern for some schemes and labels. However, schemes could work to better clarify their causal pathways of change on GHG emissions and links to their standards.

Nonetheless, determining whether SCS and labels used in the bioeconomy reduce GHG emissions is a complex and context-dependent question. There is insufficient robust evidence across the value chain, sectors and geographic regions in the current evidence base to definitively answer this question without further primary research.

It is worth noting that determining whether SCS are responsible for GHG emissions reductions would require establishing a counterfactual scenario, which was outside the remit of the current evidence mapping. This could be considered at a later phase through a systematic review of the evidence. Work Package 5 will also be evaluating various value chains and comparing differences between environmental impacts of certified and non-certified subjects as part of their investigations, which will complement this report's findings. A wider mapping exercise of the impacts of other market-based-approaches (see Conceptual

framework) would also complement knowledge about efforts to reduce GHG emissions in this field.

The dearth of impacts evidence on bio-based value chains is especially apparent when we consider the specific boundaries of the STAR4BBS project (i.e., excluding food, feed, and bioenergy would further reduce the evidence base significantly). It is not possible to know for sure whether this will be the case for other thematic areas of interest to STAR4BBS without a similar mapping exercise, however, we can assume that a topic as high-profile as GHG emissions contains one of the largest evidence bases. The implication for the Joint Monitoring System (JMS) under development by STAR4BBS and its sister projects is that it cannot, at this time, afford to solely rely on impacts research to benchmark the outcomes of SCS and labels. At the same time, as one of the goals of the JMS is to support improvement of SCS and labels over time, highlighting the evidence gaps could over time encourage both scheme owners and researchers to help fill these gaps.

4 Appendix Ia – The Search Protocol

18th July 2023

Sustainability Certification Schemes and Labels in Bio-based Value Chains: Protocol for Systematic Mapping of Evidence on GHG Emissions Reduction

Background

Many voluntary sustainability systems and market-based tools have been established to address and mitigate greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. These initiatives operate in diverse ways and target various stages of the supply chain. In order to enhance support for improvement and collaboration in these efforts, the International Social and Environmental Accreditation and Labelling Alliance (ISEAL) aims to gain a comprehensive understanding of the available evidence through a systematic mapping exercise. This exercise will complement previous research conducted by Evidensia, which examined the contribution and effectiveness of sustainability systems in achieving sustainability outcomes.

This systematic evidence evaluation will focus on sustainability certification schemes and labels applicable to bio-based value chains. The European Union's (EU) shift toward a bio-based economy has raised concerns about the potential negative impacts associated with the rapid increase in demand for bio-based materials. The European Commission defines bioeconomy as: “The bioeconomy means using renewable biological resources from land and sea, like crops, forests, fish, animals and micro-organisms to produce food, materials and energy” (European Commission, 2018).

It has become evident that only sustainably developed circular bio-based systems possess the potential to fulfil key priorities such as achieving climate neutrality and zero pollution. Consequently, new international and national regulations, initiatives, and agreements are being implemented to manage the trade-offs along bio-based value chains.

Recognizing the significance of sustainability certification schemes and labels in guiding this transition, the EU Commission acknowledges their pivotal role in supporting compliance with new legislation, particularly in terms of reducing GHG emissions. Therefore, ISEAL aims to gather comprehensive evidence through the systematic map to provide insights into the effectiveness of sustainability certification schemes and labels within bio-based value chains of reducing GHG emissions. The systematic map will contribute to the development of informed policies and initiatives that can address the challenges associated with the sustainable growth of bio-based economies and mitigate potential adverse effects on the environment.

Stakeholder engagement

This systematic map forms one of the background tasks for the EU Horizon-funded project Sustainability Transition Assessment Rules for Bio-Based Systems (STAR4BBS) (www.star4bbs.eu), which is comprised of a consortium of 10 institutions and sustainability systems. As such, the consortium was consulted at various points during the development of the search protocol from conception. Stakeholders were consulted as a group formally and informally via 1-2-1s and e-mail, with formal presentations including:

- 14th September 2022: Project kick-off meeting, Berlin, ~25 participants
- 7th March 2023: General assembly meeting, virtual, ~25 participants
- 12th June 2023: Systematic mapping coordination meeting (with sister projects), virtual, 12 participants
- 27th June 2023: June quarterly meeting, virtual, 24 participants

Stakeholders shaped the thematic focus of the mapping, and contributed keywords and concepts which will be adapted for use in the search strategy.

Objective of the review

The aim of this systematic map is to examine the available evidence on sustainability certification schemes and labels applicable to bio-based value chains in reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions within bio-based value chains. Sector-specific differences in their impact on GHG emissions will also be explored. An important feature of the systematic map is to identify gaps and limitations in the current evidence base.

Primary question

1. Do sustainability certification schemes and labels, used in the bioeconomy, reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions?

Sub-question(s):

- a) Are there differences between different sectors of the bioeconomy?
- b) Are there differences between the production of raw materials compared with other parts of the value chain in the bioeconomy?
- c) Are there differences in the primary tools adopted by certification schemes and labels to track GHG emissions?
- d) Where are there significant knowledge gaps in the evidence base in this field of study?

A PICO framework has been used to categorise the different aspects of both the primary and secondary questions (Table 1).

Table 1: Definitions of the question (PICO)

Element	Description
Population	Value chains in the bioeconomy - from producers of primary feedstock to consumers of bio-based products, in any geographic location. Feedstock to include primary agricultural (including horticulture, beekeeping, silk production, etc.), forestry, marine products; biological waste material or residues.
Intervention	Sustainability certification schemes and labels (applicable to the bioeconomy)
Comparator	A different/ absence of sustainability certification scheme(s) or label(s) applicable to the bioeconomy (see further information in the inclusion criteria).
Outcome	GHG emissions

Methods

Search strategy

Bibliographic databases

The search strategy will be designed to maximize the amount of relevant literature found by following best practice guidelines outlined in Livoreil et al. (2017). An iterative approach will be applied to identify, improve, and optimize keywords and search terms (Paivinen et al 2023). The initial list of terms provided by the client on the 24th of May 2023 will be utilized as the baseline for Search Optimization. These terms will be expanded upon through the identification of synonyms and related terms from relevant literature. This extensive list of keywords and terms will then be optimized against a test set of 15 relevant articles (Appendix PI) to ensure the maximum return of relevant literature while reducing the overall quantity of irrelevant literature, i.e., a good balance of precision and accuracy. The terms from the optimized search will be combined into one or more Boolean strings and used to search three online bibliographic databases (Table 2).

Searches of the online bibliographic databases and aggregates will be conducted in English only (articles returned in other languages will be assessed where possible). While clearly limiting complete comprehensiveness of reviews, justification for imposing this common limitation is provided in research by Ramírez-Castañeda (2020) that reports 98% of academic publications in science are written in English. A pragmatic decision, based on resource availability, to

limit searches to the English language does not, therefore, overly limit the integrity of the current systematic map.

The three bibliographic databases (Web of Science, CAB Abstracts, and Scopus) were chosen because they have high coverage rates of journals of relevance to the bioeconomy, and other publications with relevant content.

Grey literature

Recognising the importance of including non-journal articles (grey literature) for minimizing possible biases in systematic reviews and maps (Haddaway & Bayliss, 2015), the systematic map will adopt a three-pronged approach (Table 2):

1. articles from other sources (reports, conferences, books) will be searched via CAB Abstracts.
2. institutional websites of relevant organisations will be searched for articles of interest.
3. a call for grey literature will be made to stakeholders to supplement articles retrieved through other searches.

Time and resources will not permit the examination of these databases.

Table 2: List of sources of literature to be searched

Source of literature	Resource	Location
Online Bibliographic Databases & Aggregators	Web Of Science (Core collection)	www.webofscience.com/
	CAB Abstracts	https://www.cabi.org/
	Scopus	https://www.scopus.com/
Research Organisations' & Stakeholders	Direct outreach (emails)	(See Appendix PII)

Table 3: Key words/terms used to search bibliographic databases

PICO Element	Key Term
Population	Agriculture aquaculture banana bio-based chemicals bioplastics construction coffee cocoa forestry furniture marine pharmaceuticals rubber textiles wood products algae barley by-catch by-products cassava castor

	<p>oil cork corn cotton fermentation by-product fishery by-product flax fibre forestryresidue hemp jute maize manure meat by-product meat fat miscanthus natural fibers oats oil crop oil palm oil-seed by-product olive oil organic municipal solid waste organic waste paper waste peanut shell potatoes pulp rapeseed residues of biological origin residues of non-biological origin rice husk rubber rye soybean starch by-product Starch crops straw sugar sugar cane sugar beet sugar cane straw sunflower seed tall oil tea textile residue textile waste waste material wheat wood wood chip afforestation agroforestry agronomist biorefinery buyer certifier chemical recycler company consumer cooperative cultivator distributor exporter farmer grower processor producer rancher regulator retailer smallholder trader transporter wholesaler biobased economy biochemical bioeconomy biomass biomaterial bioproduct Feedstock life cycle analysis manufacture LCA lifecycle analysis palm oil</p>
<p>Intervention</p>	<p>Certification certification scheme CSLs ecolabel sustainability certification sustainability label sustainability standard sustainably certified voluntary sustainability standards VSS ABNT Ecolabel ABNT Ecolabel – Hummingbird ABNT Ecolabel Hummingbird AIAB AIAB (Italian Association for Organic Agriculture) ANAB ANAB - Architettura Naturale Aquaculture stewardship council Aquaculture stewardship council (ASC) Architettura Naturale ASC ASC-MSC Seaweed Standard Assessment System for Sustainable Building Assessment System for Sustainable Building (Bewertungssystem Nachhaltiges Bauen-BNB) Austrian Ecolabel Better Biomass Better Cotton Better Cotton Claims Framework Bewertungssystem Nachhaltiges Bauen Bio-Based Content certification scheme Bioland BioRe Blue Angel Bluesign Product Bluesign Approved Material Bluesign Product Bluesign System BNB assessment system Bon Sucro Bonsucro Bra miljöval BREEAM Business and Institutional Furniture Manufacturers Association China GAP China Environmental Labeling China GAP (Global Agricultural Practice) China Global Agricultural Practice Content Claim (Textile Exchange standards) Cosmetics Organic and Natural Standard Cosmetics Organic and Natural Standard COSMOS natural COSMOS organic Cotton made in Africa Cradle to Cradle Cradle to Cradle standard Deutsche Gesellschaft für Nachhaltiges Bauen DGNB DGNB (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Nachhaltiges Bauen) DIN-Geprüft biobased DIN-Geprüft biobased ECC Eco Label Sri Lanka Eco Mark Program Eco-</p>

	<p>Certified Composite Eco-Certified Composite (ECC) Eco- Labelling - Republic of Kazakhstan Eco-Labelling Republic of Kazakhstan ECOCERT ECOCERT Natural Detergents ECOCERT Natural Detergents and Natural Detergents made with Organic ECOCERT Natural Detergents made with Organic Ecopelle Ekolabel Indonesia Environmental Choice New Zealand EU Ecolabel EU Organic Agriculture European Union Ecolabel European Union Organic Agriculture Fair for Life Fair Trade Certified Fairtrade Certified Fairtrade International Textile Standard Fairtrade International Trader Forest Stewardship Council FSC 100% FSC Chain of Custody FSC Forest management Certification FSC Mixed FSC FSC Chain of Custody FSC CoC FSC Construction project FSC Forest management Certification FSC Mixed FSC Recycled GGN Label Global Seafood Alliance Best Aquaculture Practices Global Organic Textile Standard Global Organic Textile Standard (GOTS) Global Seafood Alliance Global Seafood Alliance - Best Aquaculture Practices Global G.A.P Global G.A.P Integrated Farm Assurance Global G.A.P Integrated Farm Assurance Aquaculture Global G.A.P. Integrated Farm Assurance Certification Global G.A.P. Integrated Farm Assurance - Aquaculture Good Environmental Choice Australia GoodWeave GoodWeave International Generic Standard GOTS Green Building Initiative Green Button Green Choice Philippines Green Crane Green Crane -Ucrania- Green Gold Label Green Mark Program Green Seal GreenPro GreenPro (India) GreenPro India Hong Kong Green Label Scheme Hong Kong Green Label Scheme IFOAM IFOAM Organic Indonesian Sustainable Palm Oil Indonesian Sustainable Palm Oil (ISPO) International Federation of Organic Agriculture Movements ISCC PLUS ISPO Israeli Green Label Italian Association for Organic Agriculture Japanese Biomass plastic identification labelling system Japanese Biomass plastic identification labeling system Korean Eco-Label Program Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design (LEED) Leaf Marque Leather standard by OEKO-TEX LEATHER STANDARD by OEKO-TEX LEED LEVEL by BIFMA Living Building Malaysian Sustainable Palm Oil Malaysian Sustainable Palm Oil (MSPO) Marine Stewardship Council Marine Stewardship Council - MSC Milieukeur Minergie- ECO MSC MSPO NATRUE Natural Cosmetics Nature Care Product NaturePlus Naturland Naturleder IVN certified Naturtextil IVN certified BEST NEN Bio-Based Content Nordic Ecolabel OCS OEKO-TEX OEKO-TEX ECO PASSPORT OEKO-TEX Made in Green OEKO-TEX STeP OEKO- TEX ECO PASSPORT OEKO-TEX STeP OK Biodegradable OK Compost industrial OK Biobased OK Biodegradable -soil- -</p>
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	<p>water- -marine- OK Biodegradable marine OK Biodegradable soil OK Biodegradable water OK Compost OK Compost - industrial- -home- OK Compost home On the way to PlanetProof Organic Content Standard Organic Content Standard OCS (Textile Exchange standards) Pacific Organic Standard PEFC PEFC certified label PEFC Forest Management PEFC PROJECT Chain of Custody PEFC Project Chain of Custody PEFC Project CoC PEFC recycled label Plant Dyes Standard Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification Forest Management Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification Chain of Custody Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification (PEFC) Chain of Custody Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification (PEFC) Forest Management Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification CoC Rainforest Alliance REDCert Responsible Alpaca Standard (Textile Exchange standards) Responsible Down Standard (Textile Exchange standards) Responsible Mohair Standard (Textile Exchange standards) Responsible Wool Standard (Textile Exchange standards) Roundtable on Sustainable Biomaterials Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil (RSPO) Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil (RSPO) Roundtable on Sustainable Soy RSB Global Advanced Products Certification RSPO SBP SFI Forest Management Certification SFI Certified Sourcing Certification SFI Certified Sourcing Certification SFI Chain-of-Custody Certification SFI CoC SFI Fibers Sourcing Certification SFI Forest Management Certification Singapore Green Labelling Scheme SIRIM Eco-Labelling Scheme Malaysia SIRIM Eco-Labelling Scheme Malaysia Standard 100 by OEKO-TEX STANDARD 100 by OEKO-TEX Sustainable Biomass Program Sustainable Biomass Program (SBP) Sustainable Fibre Alliance Sustainable Florists Sustainable Forestry Initiative Swedish Good Environmental Choice -Bra miljöva- Swedish Good Environmental Choice Ecolabel TerraChoice EcoLogo Program Textile Exchange standards Textile Exchange Content Claim Textile Exchange Responsible Alpaca Standard Textile Exchange Responsible Down Standard Textile Exchange Responsible Mohair Standard Textile Exchange Responsible Wool Standard Thai Green Label TUV Seedling TV Austria TV Rheinland TV Rheinland Green Product Mark UEBT Ukraine Green Crane UL Ecologo Certification UL ECOLOGO TerraChoice Union for Ethical Biobased sourcing Union for Ethical Biobased sourcing (UEBT) USDA Biobased Product Label USDA Certified Biobased Product Vitality Leaf -Russia- Vitality Leaf EcoLabel Vitality Leaf EcoLabel Russia WFTO Fair Trade Standard World Fair Trade Organisation organic</p>
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	agriculture
Comparator	N/A
Outcomes	Carbon footprint measur* Carbon footprint change embodied carbon GHG emission increase* GHG emission reduc* GHG emission* change GHG footprint Greenhouse gas* Green-house gas* Green house gas* Nitrous oxide Methane Fluorinated gas* hydrofluorocarbon* perfluorocarbon* sulfur hexafluoride* hydrochlorofluorocarbon* halocarbon* halogen* nitrogen trifluoride Carbon dioxide CO2 HCFC HFC N2O CH4 SF6 PFC NF3 emission* environmental impact

Article screening and study inclusion criteria

Screening strategy

Following searching in each of the bibliographic databases and aggregators, articles will be uploaded into EndNote20⁹, subscription reference management software published by Clarivate. Duplicate articles will be removed and the resulting combined set of articles will be uploaded into Rayyan¹⁰, a free natural-language processing tool that employs machine learning for screening articles for systematic evidence evaluation. Articles will be screened for eligibility at two stages: (i) title and abstract assessment; and (ii) full-text assessment. Screeners will assess articles and make a decision about including the article with reference to the inclusion criteria. They will always retain an article at the first stage of screening (where only the Title and Abstract of an article is assessed) if it is unclear whether the inclusion criteria have been met in full. These articles will then be assessed for inclusion at the full-text stage. At this stage, it will be clear whether an article meets the inclusion criteria in full, in which case it proceeds to the coding stage, or is excluded on the grounds of wrong Population, Wrong Intervention, Absence of or Wrong Outcome. Note that decisions based on presence of a Comparator will be assessed according to the more detailed notes below.

⁹ <https://endnote.com/>

¹⁰ <https://www.rayyan.ai/>

Consistency checking

Articles will be single- screened by 4 screeners. In order to check consistency of screening at title and abstract stage, sets of 50 articles will be screened by all screeners and inter-rater agreement will be assessed using Cohen's kappa (Altman, 1991). Differences in screening will be discussed amongst the screeners and the process repeated with sets of 50 articles until a satisfactory level of agreement is reached (0.6). From the third round of testing (inclusive) onwards, the number of articles will rise to 100. At full-text screening, sets of 2 articles will be similarly assessed by all screeners until inter-rater agreement is reached. During the screening and coding processes, notes will be assembled to guide other screeners and coders, and included as an Appendix to the Protocol as a living document to ensure consistency and efficiency (Appendix PIII).

Inclusion criteria

In order to be included in the review, articles must include information from the population, intervention and outcome sections of the PICO framework (Table 1). Inclusion criteria are detailed in Table 4. Exclusion criteria are noted in Table 5.

Table 4: Inclusion criteria

Inclusion Criteria	Description
Population	Value chains in the bioeconomy - from producers of primary feedstock to consumers of bioproducts. Feedstock to include primary agriculture (including horticulture, beekeeping, silk production, etc.), forestry, marine products; biological waste material or residues.
Intervention	Studies examining certification schemes and labels in the bioeconomy
Outcomes	GHG emission (any reported greenhouse gas, combination of gases or reports of unspecified greenhouse gases)
Geographic Scope	Include all geographical regions
Publication Type	Published studies, reports, articles, conference proceedings, and grey literature sources
Date	Studies published after and including 2010

Exclusion criteria

Table 5: Exclusion criteria

Exclusion Criteria	Description
Population	Studies not addressing value chains in the bioeconomy. Biofuels and bioenergy, except where the focus is on the production of the feedstock.
Interventions	Studies not addressing sustainability certification schemes and labels applicable to the bioeconomy.
Outcomes	Studies not addressing GHG emissions
Publication Type/ Study Design	Unpublished materials, personal communications, opinions, editorials, and letters without original research data, systematic reviews, routine monitoring reports, descriptive resources, and modelling studies that examine future scenarios using third-party data.
Date	Studies published before 2010.

Risk of bias assessment

Full-text studies will be evaluated for appropriateness of the study design for the research question, and an assessment of specific criteria related to the study design and will use checklists adapted from the Joanna Briggs Institute¹¹. The evaluation will be conducted without consideration of the study results to avoid interpretation bias. The following questions will be posed for risk of bias assessment:

- Are there any missing data? (Are data collected in the Methods section of a study all reported in the Results section).
- Are all missing data accounted for? (If there are unreported data does the author explain why they have not reported them).
- Are the study subjects and the setting described in detail?

¹¹ <https://jbi.global/critical-appraisal-tools>

- Is the intervention(s) described including details of certification timing, and duration?
- Is there a clear account of the statistical methods used to compare groups for all outcome(s)?
- Are all raw data available?

The results of these assessments will not be used for excluding studies from the evidence map, but are intended to enable filtering of studies at risk of bias from specific analyses.

Data coding and extraction strategy

Data from the included studies will be extracted and summarised in a standardised evidence table (Appendix PIV). In addition to metadata about the article (authors, title, date of publication, source, abstract) taken directly from the bibliographic databases, and study design details, coded by the review team, information based on the PICO elements will be extracted by the review team. Geographic location data (latitude/longitude expressed in decimal degrees) will either be taken directly from the article or added using <https://www.latlong.net/> to look up locations of place names in the article. Articles which provide data for multiple interventions will be treated as separate ‘studies’. Consistency amongst coders and data extractors will be assessed in the same way as full-text article screening, and differences will be resolved by repeated discussion until agreement is reached.

Data synthesis and presentation

Data for date and source of publication, location of study, and study design will be summarised in a series of tables and figures. Geographic regions will be used to group and present data following the United Nations Statistical Division guidelines (United Nations, 1999). A narrative discussion of results highlighting the evidence gaps and putting forth recommendations will be synthesised from the included evidence base.

Appendix PI

Table PIi – Test set of articles

Morão, A., de Bie, F., 2019. Life Cycle Impact Assessment of Polylactic Acid (PLA) Produced from Sugarcane in Thailand
De Rosa, M., Schmidt, J., Pasang, H., 2022. Industry-driven mitigation measures can reduce GHG emissions of palm oil, doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.132565
Nhu, T.T., Schaubroeck, T., Henriksson, P.J., Bosma, R., Sorgeloos, P., Dewulf, J., 2016. Environmental impact of non-certified versus certified (ASC) intensive Pangasius

aquaculture in Vietnam, a comparison based on a statistically supported LCA, doi:10.1016/j.envpol.2016.10.006
Morris, C., 2021. Study of greenhouse gas emissions of Better Cotton
Schmidt, J., De Rosa, M., 2020. Certified palm oil reduces greenhouse gas emissions compared to non-certified, doi:doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.124045
Beldman, A., Pishgar-Komleh, S.H., Termeer, E., 2021. Mitigation options to reduce GHG emissions at dairy and beef farms, doi:10.1080/20430779.2013.840200
Keller, E.J., Milà i Canals, L., King, H., Lee, J., Clift, R., 2013. Agri-food certification schemes: how do they address greenhouse gas emissions?, doi:10.1080/20430779.2013.840200
Saswattecha, K., Cuevas Romero, M., Hein, L., Jawjit, W., Kroeze, C., 2015. Non-CO2 greenhouse gas emissions from palm oil production in Thailand, doi:10.1080/1943815X.2015.1110184
Saswattecha, K., Kroeze, C., Jawjit, W., Hein, L., 2015. Assessing the environmental impact of palm oil produced in Thailand, doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2015.03.037
Meijer, K.S., 2015. A comparative analysis of the effectiveness of four supply chain initiatives to reduce deforestation
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Appendix PII

Table PIIi - Names of organisations including Standards and Labels issuing bodies. (as supplied by ISEAL)

ABNT Ecolabel	Bluesign Product	Nachhaltiges Bauen
ABNT Ecolabel Hummingbird	Bluesign Approved Material	DGNB
AIAB (Italian Association for Organic Agriculture)	Bluesign Product	(Deutsche Gesellschaft für Nachhaltiges Bauen
ANAB	Bluesign System	DIN-Geprüft biobased
ANAB - Architettura Naturale	BNB assessment system	ECC
Aquaculture stewardship council (ASC)	Bon Sucro/Bonsucro	Eco Label Sri Lanka
Architettura Naturale	Bra miljöval	Eco Mark Program
ASC-MSC Seaweed Standard	BREEAM	Eco-Certified Composite (ECC)
Assessment System for Sustainable Building	Business and Institutional Furniture Manufacturers Association	Eco-Labeling - Republic of Kazakhstan
Assessment System for Sustainable Building (Bewertungssystem Nachhaltiges Bauen-BNB)	China GAP	ECOCERT
Austrian Ecolabel	China Environmental Labeling	ECOCERT Natural Detergents
Better Biomass	China GAP (Global Agricultural Practice)	ECOCERT Natural Detergents made with Organic
Better Cotton	China Global Agricultural Practice	Ecopelle
Better Cotton Claims Framework	Content Claim (Textile Exchange standards)	Ekolabel Indonesia
Bewertungssystem Nachhaltiges Bauen	Cosmetics Organic and Natural Standard	Environmental Choice New Zealand
Bio-Based Content certification scheme	COSMOS natural	EU Ecolabel
Bioland	COSMOS organic	EU Organic Agriculture
BioRe	Cotton made in Africa	European Union Ecolabel
Blue Angel	Cradle to Cradle	European Union Organic Agriculture
	Cradle to Cradle standard	Fair for Life
	Deutsche Gesellschaft für	Fair Trade Certified

Fairtrade Certified
Fairtrade International Textile Standard
Fairtrade International Trader
Forest Stewardship Council (FSC)
FSC Chain of Custody
FSC Mixed
FSC 100%
FSC Chain of Custody
FSC CoC
FSC Construction project
FSC Forest management Certification
FSC Mixed
FSC Recycled
GGN Label
Global Seafood Alliance Best Aquaculture Practices
Global Organic Textile Standard (GOTS)
Global Seafood Alliance
Global Seafood Alliance - Best Aquaculture Practices
Globalgap
Globalgap Integrated Farm Assurance
Globalgap Integrated Farm Assurance Aquaculture
Globalgap Integrated Farm Assurance Certification
Good Environmental Choice

Australia
GoodWeave
GoodWeave International Generic Standard
GOTS
Green Building Initiative
Green Button
Green Choice Philippines
Green Crane
Green Crane -Ucrania-
Green Gold Label
Green Mark Program
Green Seal
GreenPro
GreenPro India
Hong Kong Green Label Scheme
IFOAM
IFOAM Organic
Indonesian Sustainable Palm Oil (ISPO)
International Federation of Organic Agriculture Movements
ISCC PLUS
ISPO
Israeli Green Label
Italian Association for Organic Agriculture
Japanese Biomass plastic identification labelling system

Korean Eco-Label Program
Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design (LEED)
Leaf Marque
Leather standard by OEKO-TEX
LEATHER STANDARD by OEKO-TEX
LEED
LEVEL by BIFMA
Living Building
Malaysian Sustainable Palm Oil (MSPO)
Marine Stewardship Council - MSC
Milieukeur
Minergie-ECO
MSPO
NATRUE
Natural Cosmetics
Nature Care Product
NaturePlus
Naturland
Naturleder IVN certified
Naturtextil IVN certified BEST
NEN Bio-Based Content
Nordic Ecolabel
OCS
OEKO-TEX
OEKO-TEX ECO PASSPORT
OEKO-TEX Made in Green

OEKO-TEX SteP
OEKO-TEX® ECO PASSPORT
OK Biodegradable
OK Compost industrial
OK Biobased
OK Biodegradable marine
OK Biodegradable soil
OK Biodegradable water
OK Compost
OK Compost home
On the way to PlanetProof
Organic Content Standard
Organic Content Standard OCS (Textile Exchange standards)
Pacific Organic Standard
PEFC
PEFC certified label
PEFC Forest Management
PEFC Project Chain of Custody
PEFC recycled label
Plant Dyes Standard
Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification Forest Management
Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification Chain of Custody
Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification (PEFC)

Chain of Custody
Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification (PEFC) Forest Management
Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification CoC
Rainforest Alliance
REDcert
Responsible Alpaca Standard (Textile Exchange standards)
Responsible Down Standard (Textile Exchange standards)
Responsible Mohair Standard (Textile Exchange standards)
Responsible Wool Standard (Textile Exchange standards)
Roundtable on Sustainable Biomaterials
Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil (RSPO)
Roundtable on Sustainable Soy
RSB Global Advanced Products Certification
SBP
SFI Forest Management Certification
SFI Certified Sourcing Certification
SFI Chain-of-Custody Certification
SFI CoC
SFI Fibers Sourcing

Certification
SFI Forest Management Certification
Singapore Green Labelling Scheme
SIRIM Eco-Labeling Scheme Malaysia
Standard 100 by OEKO-TEX
Sustainable Biomass Program (SBP)
Sustainable Fibre Alliance
Sustainable Florists
Sustainable Forestry Initiative (SFI)
Swedish Good Environmental Choice -Bra miljöva-
Swedish Good Environmental Choice Ecolabel
TerraChoice EcoLogo Program
Textile Exchange standards
Textile Exchange Content Claim
Textile Exchange Responsible Alpaca Standard
Textile Exchange Responsible Down Standard
Textile Exchange Responsible Mohair Standard
Textile Exchange Responsible Wool Standard
Textile Exchange standards
Thai Green Label
TUV Seedling

TV Austria
TV Rheinland
TV Rheinland Green Product Mark
UEBT
Ukraine Green Crane

UL Ecologo Certification
UL ECOLOGO® TerraChoice
Union for Ethical Biotrade sourcing (UEBT)
USDA Biobased Product Label
USDA Certified Biobased

Product
Validity Leaf EcoLabel
Validity Leaf EcoLabel Russia
WFTO Fair Trade Standard
World Fair Trade Organisation

Table Plii - Names of organisations to be contacted directly

Bonsucro
RSPO
Aquaculture Stewardship Council (ASC)
Better Cotton
Roundtable for Sustainable Biomaterials (RSB)
Textile Exchange
Rainforest Alliance
Forest Stewardship Council (FSC)
Fairtrade

Appendix PIII – Support for screeners and coders

Inclusion Criteria	Description
Population	Value chains in the bioeconomy - from producers of primary feedstock to consumers of bioproducts. Feedstock to include primary agriculture (including horticulture, beekeeping, silk production, etc.), forestry, marine products; biological waste material or residues.
Intervention	Studies examining certification schemes and labels in the bioeconomy
Outcomes	GHG emission (any reported greenhouse gas, combination of gases or reports of unspecified greenhouse gases)
Geographic Scope	Include all geographical regions
Publication Type	Published studies, reports, articles, conference proceedings, and grey literature sources
Date	Studies published after and including 2010

Exclusion Criteria	Description
Population	Studies not addressing value chains in the bioeconomy
Interventions	Studies not addressing sustainability certification schemes and labels applicable to the bioeconomy.
Outcomes	Studies not addressing GHG emissions
Publication Type/ Study Design	Unpublished materials, personal communications, opinions, editorials, and letters without original research data, systematic reviews, routine monitoring reports, descriptive resources, and modelling studies that examine future scenarios using third-party data.
Date	Studies published before 2010.

1. Does the article have an outcome - GHG emissions? If yes move to question Q2
2. Does the article refer to a sustainability standard/label in a biobase industry? If no move to Q3. If yes move to Q4
3. Does the article refer to a market based tool? If yes mark with an EX for extended and exclude using the appropriate framework letter.
4. Does the article compare a sustainability standard/label with a non-standard/label or another standard/label? If yes include the article and fully code. If no mark with none in comparator.

If unsure about any answer include and assess at full text.

Definitions

Bioeconomy

The bioeconomy covers all sectors and systems that rely on biological resources (e.g. animals, plants, micro-organisms and derived biomass, including organic waste).

It includes and interlinks the following: land and marine ecosystems and the services they provide; all primary production sectors that use and produce biological resources (e.g. agriculture, forestry, fisheries, and aquaculture); and all economic and industrial sectors that use biological resources and processes to produce bio-based products, and services.

Bio-based value chains

- A value chain can either start from an initial renewable feedstock to produce different bio-based end-products or target a specific bio-based end-product that can be produced from various renewable feedstocks
- It also includes residues at all life-cycle stages including by-products and end of life waste streams
- It include bio-based intermediates/products that are fully bio-based (e.g. functional chemicals and drop-in chemicals)

Sector exclusions (treatment of biofuels and bioenergy)

Literature focusing on the biofuels sector itself or sectors/applications of fuel use are not relevant and should be excluded (e.g. aviation, transportation, batteries, engines, electric vehicles, testing of biofuels etc)

However, if a paper looks at the production of biomass for biofuels or bioenergy (e.g papers on production or certification of sugarbeet, palm oil, sugar cane etc) it is of interest. At the title and abstract stage, please include these papers and they will be reviewed again at the full-text stage.

Please take a precautionary approach to biofuels/bioenergy and include if unsure.

Example sectors to be included (indicative, not exhaustive):

Sectors producing feedstocks e.g.

- Agriculture and horticulture (incl. Animal farming and industrial crops)
- Fisheries, aquaculture, and other aquatic biomass producers (incl. algae)
- Forestry and silviculture
- Organic by-products and waste streams from any industrial sector (incl. Municipal and consumer waste)

Intermediate products e.g.

- Organic acids (e.g. lactic acid)
- Alcohols (e.g. bioethanol)
- Biopolymers (e.g. PHAs, PLAs, cellulose)
- Composite materials and bio-based components (e.g. surfactants, solvents etc)

Industrial sectors producing final goods e.g.

- Chemicals, paints and coatings
- Construction (specifically building materials)
- Cosmetics, home care, hygiene products
- Furniture
- Packaging
- Bioplastics
- Pulp and paper
- Textiles

Market-based tools:

Market-based tools are instruments or programmes that use markets, price, and other economic variables to provide incentives to reduce or eliminate negative environmental externalities. They are regulations that encourage behaviour through market signals rather than through explicit directives regarding pollution control levels or methods.

We are interested in papers that include these tools (and meet the population, and outcome) but don't include sustainability schemes and labels for the extended protocol.

Examples

An indicative, but non-exhaustive list is included below:

- Cable
- Carbon Compliance Tracker
- Carbon Disclosure Project (CDP)
- Carbon Footprint Analyzer
- Carbon Offset Exchange
- Carbon Offsetting Registry
- Carbon Portfolio Optimizer

- CarbonXchange
- Climate Action Marketplace
- Climate Asset Registry
- Climate Disclosure Standards Board (CDSB)
- Climate Impact Index
- Climate Neutral Group
- Cool Farm Tool
- EcoBalance
- EmissionTracker
- ESG Performance Tracker
- Forest500
- GHG Protocol
- Global Forest Watch
- Gold Standard
- Green Bonds Platform
- Green Market Meter
- Integrity Council for the Voluntary Carbon Market (ICVCM)
- International Cost Management Standard (ICMS)
- Low Carbon Rating
- Net Zero Navigator
- One Carbon World
- Reducing Greenhouse Gas Emissions at Farm Level
- Renewable Energy Credit
- Science-Based Targets Initiative (SBTIs)
- Tropical Forest Alliance
- VCMII
- Verified Carbon Standard (VCS)

Appendix PIV

Table PIVi: Extractable fields

id
title
journal_name
Volume
Issue
Pages
author(s)
url
Language
published_abstract (verbatim)
doi
Inclusion/ Reason For Exclusion

Notes on inclusion/exclusion
source
full_text_available
evidensia_coder
resource_type
resource_sub_type
citation
publication_date
publisher
geography
centroid_coordinates_level
country

centroid_coordinates
sdg_focus
sustainability_dimension
sustainability_issue
outcome_of_interest
cross_cutting_lens
sector
product
approach
tool
organic certification confirmed in text
evidence_type
evidence_sub_type_number
evidence_sub_type_name
data_source
funding_source
Study Duration (months)
Study Date(s) (Start)
Study Date(s) (End)
Mentions Market Based Tool? (that is not a certification or label)
Comparator
Commentary around status of certification of study subjects - (including date Certification scheme/label achieved)

Impact of certification scheme/label (narrative text copied from paper)
GHG - which gas(es)
Value chain actors (life cycle stage)
Are there any missing data?
Are all missing data accounted for?
Were the study subjects and the setting described in detail?
Was the intervention(s) described including details of certification timing, and duration?
Was there a clear account of the statistical/analytical methods used to compare groups for all outcome(s)?
All Raw Data Available?

5 Appendix Ib – Notes on the extraction sheet

Notes on the extraction sheet (see Appendix II - Supplementary data)

- **Tool (columns AI):** Because the term 'organic' is used casually, there are many different standards, and it is not always possible to tell from the text whether the subject is certified organic. We have chosen to include all texts that discuss organic subjects. We have included these under the umbrella of International Federation of Organic Agriculture Movements (IFOAM), as all other certification/practices should flow from this standard. However, this goes some way to explaining the larger representation of texts on organic subjects.
- **Study dates and duration (columns AO-AQ):** Many studies were LCAs, using data collected previously (e.g., over a few seasons, over a few years). As, in these cases, it's not clear when the LCA was conducted, we have coded these columns to have the data collection dates. More details are included in comments on the relevant cells.
- **Comparator (column AS):** Many papers did not compare two tools, but rather compared a tool to Business As Usual (BAU) or conventional/uncertified systems. In these cases, the comparator has been coded as "none" but a note has been left on the relevant cells with more detail.
- **Commentary around status of certification of study subjects (column AT):** Generally, there was very little information about the details of subjects' certification status, though there was much more about the subjects generally. We have opted to include more extensive tracts of text in column AT than strictly necessary to give a sense of the imbalance.
- **Impact of certification scheme (column AU):** It was not always possible to extract a single sentence that made sense without context. We have therefore opted to include more extensive tracts of text in column AU than was strictly necessary.
- **GHG – which gas(es) (column AV):** Many papers discuss emissions in terms of CO₂ equivalents. Where this is the case, the which gases column has been coded with GHG (unspecified) and any other mentioned gases included below.
- **Value chain actors (column AW):** A number of the studies were cradle-to-gate, but also included transport from the processing stage to the customer (use phase not included). We have coded these texts as "production" + "manufacture" or "production" + "processing", but have not disaggregated further.
- **Missing data (columns AX and AY):** The "Are all missing data accounted for?" column has been left blank when there was no missing data, to avoid confusion.
- **Systematic reviews:** Systematic reviews have not been included in this mapping. However, there were many captured in the search that we thought it could be useful to come back to. Please contact us for these details as exclusions are not included in Appendix II.

General observations

- **Study designs:** Generally, the studies are not set up as strict experiments (there are a few exceptions), and are loosely comparing sites (usually farms) in the same regions. There is only one included study collecting data before and after an intervention.
- **Exclusions:**
 - **Built environment:** A large number of the original papers were on the built environment, but most have been excluded because either the population was the whole building (i.e., not bio-based), or the focus was on energy efficiency. Where the focus was on materials it was not possible to extract relevant information on the bio-based building materials (e.g., timber)
 - **Palm oil:** There were a body of literature that looked at tangential issues that cause emissions in the palm oil sector and are addressed by RSPO, ISPO, MSPO etc. These included most prominently Land Use Land Cover Change, Palm Oil Mill Effluent (POME), and cultivation of peat lands, however, the link with emissions was implicit, so they were excluded.
 - **Schemes' GHG calculators:** There were a couple of studies that compared different schemes' emissions calculators (RSB, RSPO, Bonsucro) and the discrepancies between their measurements. The studies had implications for reducing emissions because you could immediately superficially reduce emissions by switching the tool, but we judged this was tangential to the mapping's aims and excluded these papers.

Grey literature & ISEAL members' activities:

We have not been able to include ISEAL members' reports (or self-produced reports of other SCS and labels of interest) in the coding sheet, but would like to highlight the following:

Bonsucro:

- Undertaking a lot of work on GHGs from sugarcane, with recent updates to GHG calculation methodologies. There are some GHG reduction figures included in Bonsucro's [outcome reports](#), and this year's outcome report will be published in October using the new calculation methodology.
- They are one of the schemes that have developed a GHG calculator, along with RSB and RSPO.
- Bonsucro are also piloting a sugarcane pathway tool to support organizations to set science-based targets.
- Bonsucro highlighted the following additional resources, which the team did not have time to review:
 - Bonsucro climate action hub webpage, with infographic: <https://bonsucro.com/climate-action/>
 - Bonsucro science-based targets project [webpage summary](#), [factsheet](#), project plan [webinar](#) and [public consultation documents](#) (draft deliverables)

Aquaculture Stewardship Council (ASC):

- Have a workstream dedicated to GHG projects but no publicly available reporting

Better Cotton:

- Shared the Anthesis study, which they commissioned 2 years ago and is publicly available here : [Better Cotton Releases First Study on GHG Emissions - Better Cotton](#)
One of the conclusion of the study is that Better Cotton cotton related emissions are 19% lower compared to conventional.
- Better Cotton also highlighted that they a) have a clear [GHG reduction target](#) in their 2030 strategy and b) the [revised P&C](#) (effective as of season 23-24) include climate change as a cross- cutting priority.
- Better Cotton also signposted the following resource bank: www.bettercotton.org/field-level-results-impact/key-sustainability-issues/climate-change-mitigation/

6 Appendix II – Supplementary data

Please see the “Appendix II - Supplementary Data” excel for further information, including the extraction sheet.

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